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GRADUATE THESIS

The Origin of Islamic Extremism that leads to Terrorism

How to treat it in Kosovo: as War, Crime, or Disease?

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Abstract

Terrorism is a rising phenomenon which challenges states that are considered the main actors in the discipline of the International Relations (IR). It is important to understand that many countries are endangered by terrorism and that terrorists in our time, declare war on our international order that was founded with the Treaty of Westphalia in 1648. We often see it on the news that democratic states get attacked by terrorists, who kill and injure many. We also see emerging campaigns with extremist content that are thrown on the internet to radicalize people. There are cases when young Kosovars traveled to Middle East (ME) to become part of terrorist groups and fight for them. All of this is a matter of concern.

As a result, many countries have worked towards drafting different laws and strategies in order to combat this phenomenon. After the war between Kosovo and Serbia in 1998-99, the kosovar society, with little institutional experience found itself in the middle of many challenges, with Religious Extremism (RE) being one of them. Kosovo institutions addressed the rise of RE with police methods only after it was confirmed that a considerable number of Kosovo citizens had traveled to ME to become part of violent terrorist organizations. This paper aims to find out whether treating RE as crime is sufficient to address this problem in Kosovo or whether Kosovo institutions should treat the underlying symptoms that caused the rise of RE.

State institutions at some degree have managed to successfully address this phenomenon with the analogy of crime. However, the main findings of this research paper show that treating RE as crime is only a short-term solution because the arrest and imprisonment of radicalized individuals does not guarantee that their desires for jihad will also be shuttered. Therefore, in order to address terrorism in an effective way, it is important to identify the factors that lead Kosovo citizens to terrorism. For a long-term solution, this paper suggests that state institutions must concentrate more on reducing the socio-economic problems that are the underlying cause to many challenges. In order to build resilience against RE that leads to terrorism, Kosovo institutions must improve the social welfare and return people's trust in the public institutions.

Acknowledgments

On this important stage of my academic studies, as much as I am responsible for citing the different views of many authors used to complete this study; in the same way I feel responsible to thank everyone who has contributed directly and indirectly to my academic achievements. I can sincerely say that I would not be in this phase, without the support of my family, mentors and friends to whom I am deeply grateful.

I must emphasize that, in comparison to some of my fellow students who had studied the same course in the Bachelor program and were better prepared; studying for master's degree in the field of security studies has been quite challenging for me. Therefore, I must thank my professors for their patience and the knowledge that they provided through lectures, materials, and fruitful discussions. In addition, I would like to thank my classmate Drilon Hoxha, who was very helpful with suggesting and offering me proper material in order to learn more about the field of Security Studies. It would have been difficult to dedicate all this time to my studies without the financial support of my aunt, Mihrije Mustafa. She was confident to provide financial support for my college fees and that was one good reason that motivated me to successfully complete my master degree and not dissappoint her.

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Personal Statement

I, Hekuran Sokoli, enrolled in MA Security Studies program at the ISPE College, with ID No. 025/2016/MSIG, hereby declare that the masters's thesis with title: The Origin of Islamic Extremism that leads to Terrorism / How to treat it in Kosovo: as a War, as a Crime, or as a Disease? is my original work. I have not duplicated this paper from any other student's work or from any other source except for those quoted on a regular basis or for which an explicit explanation has been provided in the text.

The Declaration of Originality

With sincere feelings I declare that this work paper is my own work without any other participant being involved. All the literature and material used to construct this paper has been fully detailed in a footnote and also as it appears in the reference pages. This study is presented for the first time to the ISPE College commission, with the aim to defend my master's thesis and graduate as a final result. All the details and information used for this study are carefully perceived and written in my own words without any intention to manipulate it. However, if the supervisors of this study find any word, sentence or paragraph that is unfitting, then I would be happy to correct it.

As a beginner in the field of Security Studies, I must mention that the standpoints, conclusions and errors found in this study are personally mine; therefore I take full responsibility for it.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Prishtina, September 17, 2018

Hekuran Sokoli

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

9/11	September 11, 2001 terrorist attacks against the United States
CW	Cold War
GP	Great Powers
IC	International Community
ICK	Islamic Community of Kosovo
IE	Islamic Empire
IR	International Relations
ISIS	Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant
ME	Middle East
MJ	Ministry of Justice
OE	Ottoman Empire
RE	Religious Extremism
SU	Soviet Union
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
US	United States of America
VA	Violent Acts
VE	Violent Extremism
WWI	First World War
WWII	Second World War

1 Introduction

For many countries terrorism continues to be one of the main threats to their national security. There are many cases where the citizens of different countries got killed or wounded because terrorists committed VA based on religious, ideological, ethnic or nationalist reasons. One of the deadliest terrorist acts in world history, that pushed many states to take serious measures against terrorism, were the (9/11) attacks on the World Trade Center in New York City, orchestrated by Al Qaeda (a terrorist organization). As a result of this tragedy nearly 3,000 people were killed and more than 6,000 injured.¹ In fact, this is not new to humanity because terrorist methods have been used for many years for different political purposes. However, in the last two decades we can see that terrorism is a growing phenomenon which poses an unpredictable threat for the majority of democratic states.

Terrorism, like organized crime, uses the tools and weaknesses of the society to its advantage to achieve their goals. Terrorist organizations use the Internet to spread their ideology or to make the world look like unsafe place to live. Channels like Youtube, Facebook or Twitter have been used effectively by terrorists for recruiting individuals to join terrorist armed groups in Middle East (ME). The possibility of fast communication and travel makes it easier for these groups or individuals to commit VA and escape without being detected or caught. Another factor that terrorists use it as a weakness but in many countries is considered a value is democracy. Those democratic values may be human rights such as freedom of religion or freedom of speech and terrorists use this freedom for their misguided purposes. Therefore, terrorism poses a real threat to national security and it is very challenging for many states to fight terrorism and at the same time to remain democratic by respecting the fundamental rights of the citizens that are promised in the constitution. Due to the changing nature of terrorism, it is very important that states identify precisely the threats that come from terrorism in order to take the right measures against terrorism.

Even though it is known for its religious tolerance, some reports demonstrate that Kosovo was also affected by the Religious Extremism (RE) that later led to terrorism. With a population of 1.8 million, more than 90% of Kosovars are Muslims.² After the war with Serbia 1998-99, the early signs of RE began to appear in the Kosovar society.

1 *Nine facts about terrorism in the United States since 9/11*, (*The Washington Post*), <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/wonk/wp/2013/09/11/nine-facts-about-terrorism-in-the-united-states-since-911/?noredirect=on&utm_term=.dcfa5b55de4d> accessed 12 September 2018

2 Public Pulse, *Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo* (2017), 6.

This is due to the influence of several organizations from ME, placed in Kosovo for humanitarian reasons, some imams educated in ME and religious campaigns with radical content that was put on the internet. In 2012, it was noted that these factors have had an impact on the Kosovar society when the authorities confirmed that 316 citizens had left Kosovo to join armed groups like the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS) and Al Nusra. If we compare the number of Kosovo citizens that decided to join terrorist armed groups in ME with the number of other states, it does not seem to be that high. However, considering the fact that in Kosovo live only 1.8 million people, this number is quite concerning. Some experts claim that in the continent of Europe Kosovo has given the largest number of foreign fighters per capita.³ The methods and techniques used by terrorists are not always the same because they adapt to circumstances. They commit terrorist attacks because they are incapable or unable to make the changes that they want in society. Although scholars explain that terrorism can be based on ethnic, religious, ideological or nationalist motives; this study will concentrate on Islamic extremism that leads people to violence because currently this type of terrorism is a real threat to the national security of Kosovo and to the international security as well.

1.1 Research Theme

The world was shaken by the attacks of 9/11 and at the same time it was understood that terrorist groups are not a threat only to ME countries, but to the entire world. Based on this, the policy makers around the world globe realized the potential of terrorism; therefore, they began to devise specific policies and strategies in order to combat this phenomenon. Besides the fact that the consolidated democratic states drafted strategies and established specific measures to counter this phenomenon; due to the rapidly changing nature of terrorism, often those measures are not enough. Terrorist groups exploit the gaps of social-system to deliver a specific message or to make the society feel insecure by committing VA. In the civilized world those gaps are considered democratic values such as freedom of expression, freedom of religion, cultural diversity, freedom of movement, privacy, etc. Therefore, it is important that democratic states do not loose these values just to fight terrorism. While national and international actors are faced with the dilemma of choosing the right and proper measures to deal with terrorism, Kosovo has not remain untouched by this phenomenon.

3 Public Pulse, *Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo* (2017), 4.

This is best described in research reports, which demonstrate that from 2012 to 2013, 316 radicalized citizens left Kosovo to join foreign wars in the ME. Some scholars claim that in the continent of Europe, Kosovo has contributed with the largest number of foreign fighters who joined armed conflicts in Iraq and Syria. Having in mind that Kosovo is known for the religious tolerance values, it is important to analyze what the factors are that radicalized this society. At the same time it is important to understand if there were early signs of radicalization in Kosovo and whether it was possible to prevent this badness before it spreads its roots. Finally, it is necessary to analyze whether the Kosovo institutions are working in the right direction to prevent RE that leads people to terrorism.

1.2 Research Questions

First of all, it is essential to discuss the origin of RE and the underlying basis of existing terrorist groups or organizations that consider our international order to be unworthy and failed. Terrorism will be treated as a contemporary phenomenon that ranks as one of the main threats for the majority of democratic and non-democratic countries. It is important to analyze the spread of terrorism by considering the factors that make this phenomenon a challenge to national security and the measures that the countries take to cope with the dangers of terrorism. Second, it will be treated in a critical manner the type of terrorism that endangers the national security of Kosovo. In order to do this, it is necessary to analyze the push and pull factors that radicalized the Kosovar society. Finally, it will be discussed about the importance of choosing the right measures to deal with terrorism and analyze whether Kosovo institutions have chosen the right ones to prevent RE in Kosovo or not.

The main research question of this paper is:

- **How to treat RE in Kosovo: as war, crime or disease?**

The sub-questions of this research paper are:

- How resilient is the Kosovar society to RE?
- Was it possible to prevent RE in Kosovo?

1.2.1 Structure and Organization

The first chapter begins with the introduction of this paper and provides a brief explanation of why many states and international organizations consider terrorism as one of the main threats to their security. It describes why it is important to treat this subject. Western countries are working hard against terrorism. Yet, they have not been able to completely eliminate this phenomenon. It will also be discussed whether Kosovo was affected by terrorism and how RE found its route in a tolerant society. The second chapter will explain the birth of the Islamic faith in the 7th century and the creation of a glorious empire with its calls for universalism. The division of the Islam into two doctrines after the death of Prophet Muhammad in the year of 632 and the creation of the Ottoman Empire (OE) as a successor of Islam. It will also be elaborated the imposed formation of the states in the ME with the Sykes-Picot agreement and their tradition of autocratic governments. How the colonial period and the Cold War (CW) affected this region. The end of this chapter will point out some radical organizations in the ME that continually seek to overthrow our world order based on some calls that belong to the 7th century.

The third chapter will mainly discuss theories related to terrorism. This chapter will discuss the challenges that countries and schools of thought face when trying to define what is terrorism. There will be discussions on the types and causes of terrorism and on the facilitating factors that contribute to the spread it. The end of this chapter describes the difficulties that countries face while fighting or preventing terrorism. The preventive measures that are effective in one country may not be effective in another country. Therefore, there are several theories and standpoints related to this phenomenon. However, in this paper it will be used one of the most acceptable theories proposed by Peter Sederberg, arguing that terrorism can be seen in three ways: as a war, as a crime and as a disease. The fourth and most critical chapter of this paper will focus on the spread of RE in Kosovo. It will analyze if Kosovo institutions could not prevent the spread of RE before the year of 2012 because of the lack of legal framework or if it was a matter of negligence among authorities. Also, it describes the push and pull factors that made some Kosovars join terrorist armed groups in the region of ME. Finally, the end of this chapter analyzes how to prevent RE in Kosovo and whether Kosovo institutions are working in the right direction or not.

The fifth chapter describes the methodology of the research used in this study by giving detailed explanations on the research strategy and research process. Also, it describes the data collection process and the nature of it by considering whether this data can be reliable for the academic world. Finally, knowing that it is not possible to be explained everything about terrorism in a single work, this chapter ends with the limitations of this paper. The sixth chapter gives a brief summary of the chapters in order to discuss the main findings and analyze how they can be used in Kosovo's case. The seventh and final chapter of this paper, focuses on the historical factors of Kosovo and the push and pull factors that contributed to the radicalization of the Kosovar society. Taking into considering all the findings of this study, this chapter ends by answering the research questions and drawing the conclusions and recommendations from the research results.

Glossary

Note: All these terms are derived from the scientific publication titled “Religious Radicalism and Violent Extremism in Albania (2015) carried out by the Institute for Democracy and Mediation.

HANAFI	One of the four (Hanbali, Maliki and Shafi’i) Sunni schools of Islamic law, founded by Abu Hanifa.
JIHAD	Religious duty of Muslims – “striving in the way of God” (Qur’an). Jihad is often used as “holy war” against unbelievers to spread Islam.
RADICALIZATION	Process of developing extremist ideologies and beliefs. Radicalization may be violent or non-violent.
RELIGIOUS RADICALIZATION	Process of developing extremist religious views and beliefs.
SALAFISM	Movement within Islam that takes its name from the term Salaf (predecessors/ancestors) with literalist, strict and puritanical approaches to Islam.
SUNNI MUSLIM	Represent the largest branch of Islam (85-90% of world’s Muslim population). The remaining part of the Muslim populations (10-15%) is Shi’a Muslim.
TERRORISM	An intentional act which may seriously damage a country or an international organization, committed with the aim of seriously intimidating a population, unduly compelling a Government or an international organization to perform or abstain from performing any act, seriously destabilizing or destroying fundamental political, constitutional, economic or social structures by means of attacks upon a person’s life, attacks upon the physical integrity of a person, kidnapping, hostage-taking, seizure of aircraft or ships, or the manufacture, possession or transport of weapons or explosives. (EU Framework Decision on Combating Terrorism: 2002)
VIOLENT EXTREMISM	Process of taking radical (political, ideological or religious) views and putting them into violent action.
VIOLENT RADICALIZATION	The process of embracing opinions, views and ideas which could lead to acts of terrorism (EC:2005 “Terrorist Recruitment: addressing the factors contributing to violent radicalization”)

2 Islamism in the ME

History tells us that in the region of the ME have existed great empires who wanted to accomplish the concept of universalism by imposing their order as far as they could because each of them considered itself to be a special empire. At the end of the sixth century the ME region was dominated by the Byzantine Empire (as a successor of the Roman Empire) and Persian Empire which was spread in the territory of today's Iran. Both of these dominant empires regarded itself as centers of civilized life and sought to abolish or dominate another because that was the tradition of empires. "In 602, not long after a plague had wracked both, a Persian invasion of Byzantine territories led to a twenty-five-year-long war in which the two empires tested what remained of their strength."⁴ Due to the tribal life-style and lack of state-forming tradition, no one has ever thought that Arabs were able to form a powerful empire that would impose its own order throughout the world.

2.1 Islamic Empire

The religion of Islam teaches us about a man named Muhammad in Western Arabia (where today's Mecca lies) who received a divine vision from God when he was in his early forties. This divine vision followed Prophet Muhammad for twenty-six years and when it was written down it became known as the Qur'an book. With his cleverness he managed to convince other people that his vision was true and the right way. Therefore, they began to spread it in other places as well, the mission that was given from God. "As the Byzantine and Persian empires disabled each other, Muhammad and his community of believers organized a polity, unified the Arabian Peninsula, and set out to replace the prevailing faiths of the region—primarily Judaism, Christianity, and Zoroastrianism—with the religion of his received vision."⁵ Islamism grew in an incomparable way as a new religion and later became an empire which had charged itself with the divine mission to form a new world order. In the absence of an empire with similar dimensions to counteract the Arab army managed to spread Islam in the continent of Africa, Asia and Europe. "Each of the peoples the advancing Muslims encountered was offered the same choice: conversion, adoption of

4 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 97.

5 *Ibid.*, 98.

protectorate status, or conquest.”⁶ Considering the swiftness of the spread of Islam many societies willingly and unwillingly accepted Islam as their religion. Regions that were occupied by the Arab armies and governed by the caliphate were called dar al-Islam (House of Islam). Whereas areas that were not occupied yet by the Arab armies were called dar al-harb (Land of War) and the aim of the caliphate (as the highest institution of the empire) was to invade all those regions until the concept of universalism was entirely accomplished.

2.1.1 Jihad Strategy

The strategy to install an Islamic-based order across the world, even today, is called Jihad. The religious text of Islam states that it is an obligation for Muslim believers to fulfill their religion by spreading it in all possible directions. “Depending on the circumstances—and in various eras and regions, the relative emphasis has differed widely—the believer might fulfill jihad “by his heart; his tongue; his hands; or by the sword.”⁷ This strategy continues to be officially supported by countries like Iran and many terrorists organizations such as Al-Qaeda or the ISIS. According to their view the current international order which was founded with the Peace of Westphalia 1646-48 is a system dominated by the non-religious countries that has failed long time ago. For this reason they call on all Muslim believers to unite in combating the non-religious dominance of the world and install a new Islamic order that would bring peace to all humanity. It is important to realize that even other religions have followed such strategies that aimed to accomplish religion-based universalism. “Especially Christianity—have had their own crusading phases, at times exalting their universal mission with comparable fervor and resorting to analogous methods of conquest and forced conversions.”⁸ However, in the course of time, these strategies were understood as oppressive strategies. Therefore, people of reason wisely decided not to follow them in modern times. Different from other religions that faced the consequences of universalism concept and learned the lesson, it looks like the majority of Muslim community is not learning the lesson because, on one hand, it is praising one glorious century, but, on the other hand, it is ignoring the rest of history. To put it another way, any group or community that does not see the world as pluralistic as it is, will remain unhappy. As long as these groups who seek universalism do not overcome this concept they pose a serious threat not only in the places where they belong but also for the outside world.

6 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 99.

7 Ibid., 102.

8 Ibid., 103.

2.1.2 The Fall of the Islamic Empire

Like any other empire that had its rise and fall so has happened to the Islamic Empire (IE) after the death of Prophet Muhammad. “Following Muhammad’s passing in 632, a council of tribal elders selected his father-in-law Abu Bakr as his successor, or caliph, as the figure best able to maintain consensus and harmony in the fledgling Muslim community. A minority believed that the matter should not have been put to a vote, which implied human fallibility, and that power should have passed automatically to the Prophet’s closest blood relation, his cousin Ali—an instrumental early convert to Islam and heroic warrior whom Muhammad was held to have personally selected.”⁹ This division exists even today in the Islamic world which are the two main doctrines of Islam. The sympathizers of the Prophet’s father-in-law were named Sunni because they believed that the Prophet Muhammad’s connection with God was unique and unrepeatable. While, the sympathizers of the Prophet’s cousin Ali, were named Shia and they believed that the Prophet Muhammad’s connection with God could be resumed only by individuals with the capacity of understanding the hidden religious meanings such as Ali himself. “When Ali, eventually coming to power as the fourth caliph, was challenged by rebellion and murdered by a mob, the Sunnis treated the central task as the restoration of order in Islam and backed the faction that reestablished stability. The Shias decried the new authorities as illegitimate usurpers and lionized the martyrs who had died in resistance. These general attitudes would prevail for centuries.”¹⁰ Although divided, the Arab armies continued to pursue the jihad strategy by invading other territories and spreading Islam. However, the unstoppable rush was weakened “as the first wave of Muslim expansion was reversed in Europe. Battles at Poitiers and Tours in 732 ended an unbroken string of advances by Arab and North African Muslim forces.”¹¹

2.2 Ottoman Empire

After the fall of the IE the Muslim territories in the ME that were not invaded by the Byzantine Empire embraced their traditions and beliefs that differed from each other but they also remained nostalgic about the glorious century that had installed them the desire for global Islamic order. As a successor of the IE the OE was created in the 13th century by Turks adhering Muslim religion. This empire grew so powerful that it became bigger in

9 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 106.

10 Ibid., 106.

11 Ibid., 107.

size than all the Western European countries together and soon they managed to take over the Byzantine Empire by spreading their hierarchy with wars in all possible directions. “In 1453, they conquered Constantinople (Istanbul), the capital of Byzantium, geostrategically astride the Bosphorus Strait; next they moved south and west into the Arabian Peninsula, Mesopotamia, North Africa, Eastern Europe, and the Caucasus, becoming the dominant littoral power in the eastern Mediterranean.”¹²

2.2.1 The Rise of the OE

Similar to the early IE the OE also regarded itself as the center of civilized life that was to protect the Islamic world and spread it in all directions until the world peace was accomplished. Although they had relations with several European countries the ottomans did not accept these countries as equally homologous. The OE looked down upon these countries mainly for two reasons: (1) at that time, the OE had the most powerful army and the largest territory in the world, and (2) these countries could not be equal because they were non-Muslim. “In this context, formal Ottoman documents afforded European monarchs a protocol rank below the Sultan, the ruler of the Ottoman Empire; it was equivalent to his vizier, or chief minister. By the same token, the European ambassadors permitted by the Ottomans to reside in Constantinople were cast in the status of supplicants. Compacts negotiated with these envoys were drafted not as bilateral treaties but as unilateral and freely revocable grants of privilege by a magnanimous Sultan.”¹³ Important to mention is that during the Ottoman rule, at times, they had skipped the concept of universalism and cooperated with the other monarchs but only when it came to the interests of the Empire.

2.2.2 The Fall of the OE

The fall of the OE was not much different from the fall of the other empires. During the XIX century, as a result of internal crisis, the empire gradually began to lose control over the administered territories. There were several factors that caused dissatisfaction within the empire and eventually resulted in destabilization of it, some factors were lack of equal rights to non-Muslim communities, lack of the rights for the minorities, the rise of nationalism in the Balkans, and the aspirations of the Russian Empire to control the Slavic people in the Balkans.

12 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 107.

13 Ibid., 108.

In 1875 Balkan Serbs carried out an attack on the OE in Herzegovina and then the same attack continued in Bosnia. The organizers of this attack, with the support of Serbia and Montenegro, sought to pay less taxes to the Ottoman administration; however, this request was not taken into account by the Ottomans. As a result of the rejection, with the help of a large number of volunteer troops from Serbia and Montenegro, Serbs of Bosnia and Herzegovina continued attacking the Ottomans. The failure of the Ottoman authorities to manage the internal crisis showed the weakness of the Empire in relation to other Balkan countries. As a result, in 1876 another uprising was organized against the Ottomans in Bulgaria; the local rebels attacked Ottoman officials, police officers and civil society. This time the Ottomans decided to respond to this event quickly and in a cruel way. Considering the fact that they had sent a large number of troops to manage the crisis in Bosnia and Herzegovina, they did not have enough troops to manage the new situation in Bulgaria. In that case they decided to send the bashi-bazouks (death squads) in the face of the new crisis in Bulgaria. As a consequence, over 1,000 people were massacred during this event, as well as 5,000 residents were killed in a village called Batak. This tragic response of the OE gained tremendous attention of the media which resulted in a huge reaction from the Great Powers (GP) of that time. Considering the fact that the OE was not capable to manage its internal crisis, it lost credibility and the support of the GP; this was a great opportunity for the Russian Empire to widen its influence on the Balkan nations belonging to the Orthodox religion. Thus, in April 1877, the Russian Empire declared war on the OE with the support of Bulgaria, Romania, Serbia and Montenegro. As a result of the war Ottoman domination was diminished due to the fact that it was forced to recognize Rumania, Bulgaria, Serbia and Montenegro as independent and sovereign countries.

“The fate of its vast holdings in the Balkans and the Middle East, among them significant Christian communities with historical links to the West, became “the Eastern Question” and for much of the nineteenth century the major European powers tried to divide up the Ottoman possessions without upsetting the European balance of power.”¹⁴ For fear that Russia could become a dominant actor in Europe and also trying to avoid any possible conflict between the GP; in 1878 the representatives of six GP organized a meeting that became known as the Congress of Berlin. The purpose of this meeting was to discuss the reduced power of the OE and find a peaceful solution to divide the territories that had been under the Ottoman administration, mainly in the Balkan region.

14 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 110.

By the end of the XIX century the OE somehow played a role in the balance of power but because it was a falling power that did not have its destiny in its own hands the other GP could not count on it as a reliable partner. The Ottomans entered the First World War (WWI) claiming to support both Westphalian and Islamic order. “The Sultan accused Russia of violating the empire’s “armed neutrality” by committing an “unjustified attack, contrary to international law,” and pledged to “turn to arms in order to safeguard our lawful interests” (a quintessentially Westphalian *casus belli*). Simultaneously, the chief Ottoman religious official declared “jihad,” accusing Russia, France, and Britain of “attacks dealt against the Caliphate for the purpose of annihilating Islam” and proclaiming a religious duty for “Mohammedans of all countries” (including those under British, French or Russian administration) to “hasten with their bodies and possessions to the Djat [jihad]” or face “the wrath of God”¹⁵ Viewing from the Westphalian perspective, the OE was neither able to manage the internal crisis in the Balkan territories, nor had the capability to face the Russian Empire that was accused of violating the military neutrality. Whereas viewing from the Islamic perspective the OE was a falling power that had lost its control and the call for “jihad” to Muslim believers of all countries sounded more like a call to save the empire, than to protect the religion of Islam. Most Muslim countries that had been administered by Ottomans were much more oriented toward state formation and national interest instead of doing jihad.

2.3 Formation of States in the ME

After the end of the WWI in 1918, the Balkan countries that had been under Ottoman administration, albeit with nationalist beliefs, managed to successfully integrate into the international Westphalian order. This is mainly because at some point they have had the state tradition and therefore eagerly wanted to separate from the OE and become independent countries. Whereas the provinces in the ME that had been under the Ottoman administration neither had the state building tradition nor had a general consensus on what they want to become. Another key point may be that many of these provinces did not want to break from the Empire, not because it was a perfect system for them, but because the empire was the most advanced system that they had experienced. Therefore, the integration of this region into the Westphalian order has been and continues to be a very complex process. “Few parts of the world have been quite so buffeted by conflict and war; few parts of the world have been so much written about and debated in recent times, while remaining subject to misunderstanding and stereotype.”¹⁶

15 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 111.

16 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 1.

After the collapse of the OE the Arab provinces in the ME that had been dominated by the Ottomans were transformed into states as a result of several agreements made by the GP after the WWI. Even though it was clear that none of these newly born states had any traditions of self-government, at some point they had the tradition of reforms developed by the Ottomans as an effort to improve the lives of the people living within the empire. These Ottoman reforms in the ME became known as “Tanzimat (1839-76).”¹⁷ Also, in order to prevent the tendencies of the European powers to intervene in the internal affairs, the OE granted the Tanzimat reforms as an effort to improve the internal relations between the non-Muslim and Muslim communities. Mainly these reforms were to regulate “rational bureaucracy, fiscal regularity, a consistent rule of law, and growing contact between Ottoman subjects and their government.”¹⁸ Furthermore, “As Stanford Shaw argued, ‘Every aspect of the Ottoman system was included [in Abdulhamid II’s reform agenda]—the military, the central administration, the provinces, the law courts, finance, the economy, public works, education, fine arts, and the administration’ (Shaw and Shaw 1978: 221).¹⁹

However, all these reforms were granted to ease the Ottoman rule over its provinces and not to disengage or make them independent. It can therefore be argued that the Arab provinces had a certain administrative tradition but they did not have an experience in diplomatic relations with the international community at all because during the Ottoman rule all foreign affairs were carried out through Istanbul. When it came to deciding for their own destiny they were considered as inexperienced by the GP because they lacked a common consensus of the inter-Arab world. “The Arabs had no say in the post-war partition of their lands under League of Nations auspices, distributed among the victorious powers as a new form of colonial state known as ‘mandates’.”²⁰ When the Arab delegates participated in the Treaty of Versailles in 1919 some Arab provinces were already under the colonial rule of the GP. “Morocco, the oldest formal Arab state, became a French protectorate in 1912; Tunisia had been under French rule and Egypt under British rule since the 1880s. Algeria, the first Arab territory to come under European colonial rule (1830), was assimilated to metropolitan France and never had the chance to develop autonomous instruments of rule to the same extent as the other North

17 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 42.

18 *Ibid.*, 42.

19 *Ibid.*, 43.

20 *Ibid.*, 39.

African states.”²¹ Whereas the territories in the ME that were still under the Ottoman administration were intended to be colonized by the European GP (Britain and France) on the basis that these territories lacked the experience of self-governing. Therefore, they needed a tutelage until they are able to stand on their feet. “The Arab lands formally under Ottoman rule in 1914 were Yemen, the Red Sea province of Hijaz, Greater Syria (comprising the modern state of Syria, Lebanon, Jordan, and Israel/Palestine), and Iraq”²²

It is wrong to believe that these Arab lands were colonized because people were living there in a primitive style and the Europeans went there in order to teach them how to live. Due to the Ottoman reforms many of these provinces had government buildings “(administrative offices, courthouses, barracks), communications infrastructure (post, telegraph, roads, trams and railways), and commercial and residential quarters underwent rapid development in the later nineteenth century. Provincial capitals such as Jerusalem, Beirut, Damascus, and Baghdad were easily adapted to make national capitals in the mandates of Palestine, Lebanon, Syria, and Iraq.”²³ In the same way it is wrong to believe that the GP had planned for the destruction of the OE or the destruction of the Muslim world because history best describes that the empires had almost the same fate, they rise and fall. It can therefore be said that the OE collapsed like any other empire and the attempts of the GP were to reorganize the great territories that had been under the Ottoman rule in order to avoid any other conflict between the GP after the WWI.

2.4 Plans for the Partition of the ME

Plans for the partition of the Arab provinces that had been under the Ottoman rule began after the WWI when it was demonstrated that the empire did not have its destiny in its own hands. Under those circumstances Britain, as one of the war winning power, had launched three different kinds of negotiations for the division of territories once ruled by Ottomans. In 1915-16, Henry McMahon (British High Representative for Egypt), had negotiated with Hussein ibn Ali (Sharif of Mecca) about an Arab uprising against Ottoman forces. In return Sharif Ali had asked for British support to create an Arab kingdom that

21 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 42.

22 *Ibid.*, 42.

23 *Ibid.*, 43.

would stretch from “Mersin and Adana (in modern Turkey) to Persia in the north, to the Persian Gulf, the Indian Ocean, the Red Sea, and the Mediterranean, excluding the British colony of Aden.”²⁴ With some exceptions Commissioner McMahon had promised the British support for the creation of a such kingdom, given that Sharif Ali had begun the uprising against the OE.

During the negotiations between the aforementioned the Foreign Ministers of Britain and France had also launched negotiations for the partition of the Arab provinces ruled by the Ottomans. These negotiations were approved on February 4, 1916 and became known as the Sykes-Picot agreement because one minister was named Mark Sykes and the other Charles Francois Georges-Picot. A month later the Sykes-Picot agreement won the support of Russia as well so the three GP of that time had an agreement to respect each other’s territorial intentions. “According to this agreement, France would establish an administration in those areas that Sir Henry McMahon had excluded from the Arab kingdom—the ‘two districts of Mersina and Alexandretta and portions of Syria lying to the west of the districts of Damascus, Homs, Hama and Aleppo’—while Britain would establish an administration in Mesopotamia.”²⁵ It is noted that during this colonial rule the mandators used to manipulate the inter-Arab tensions that had been the result of historical religious and ethnic differences. “This allowed the mandating power to rule in part by manipulating tensions, in the process laying the foundation for later wars and civil wars.”²⁶ For the most part all this land was divided into influential spheres between British and French. Whereas, mainly for religious reasons and also trying to avoid disagreements between the GP, the case of Palestine would be internationalized.

2.4.1 The Balfour Declaration

The nationalist movement of the Jewish people for the formation of their own state in the present territory of Israel (at that time inhabited mainly by Arabs and known as Palestine) had begun as an initiative before the WWI but it gained support only as the war was ending. “Finally, on 2 November 1917, the British government gave formal support to the aspirations of the World Zionist Organization to establish a Jewish national home in Palestine. The Balfour declaration, transmitted in a letter from Foreign Minister Arthur

24 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 44.

25 *Ibid.*, 44-45.

26 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 112.

James Balfour to Lord Rothschild, confirmed Britain's support for the 'establishment in Palestine of a national home for the Jewish people' (Hurewitz 1979: 106).²⁷ Although the support of the British government paved the way for a country-oriented people who were rightly striving to establish their own state the manner in which this initiative was upheld was unfair. As a consequence of the poor imagination of policymaking of that time these unfair negotiations laid the foundations for four following wars and a bloody conflict between the Arab and the Jewish people, which is often thought to be a conflict without a solution. This way of negotiation contradicts the justification that the European GP colonized these ME territories because they were not able to govern themselves and needed tutelage as stated in the Convention of the League of Nations:

“Certain communities formerly belonging to the Turkish Empire have reached a stage of development where their existence as independent nations can be provisionally recognized subject to the rendering of administrative advice and assistance by a Mandatory until such time as they are able to stand alone. The wishes of these communities must be a principal consideration in the selection of the Mandatory. (Article 22)”²⁸

Given these points one can freely conclude that the Arab provinces that used to be under the Ottoman rule were treated as “spoils of war”²⁹ by the GP. In this case the mandating powers not only failed to provide tutelage to these communities. They also caused damage by treating these lands as a legacy that their fathers left them to trade and do business. For instance, the British government had selected itself as “mandate for Palestine”³⁰ and in due time had given the support to the World Zionist Organization to “establish a Jewish national home in Palestine.”³¹ Of course that the Arab community living in Palestine and elsewhere felt betrayed and opposed this agreement because they had not been involved in the negotiations and this decision was taken without their consent or approval. We can not blame the “weak bargaining position of the Arab delegates in Versailles”³² but we can point the finger at the “duplicity”³³ and the national interests of the GP. On January 8, 1918, Woodrow Wilson (the President of the United States (US)), gave a too progressive speech for that time, what is known as Fourteen Points. In the twelfth point he addressed the Arab community saying:

27 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 45.

28 *Ibid.*, 43.

29 *Ibid.*, 46.

30 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 112.

31 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 45.

32 *Ibid.*, 46.

33 *Ibid.*, 46.

“The Turkish portion of the present Ottoman Empire should be assured a secure sovereignty, but the other nationalities which are under the Turkish rule, should be assured an undoubted security of life and an absolutely unmolested opportunity of autonomous development.”³⁴

In spite of the fact the Arab delegates leaned toward Wilson’s liberal approach which promised them the opportunity of autonomous development; they failed to defend it against the delegates of the GP who had the imperial mind-set. The will of Arab delegates was not taken into consideration; instead, the GP decided for the partition of their lands under the League of Nations. This disregard of their will would be a main cause for several conflicts in the region that are still present today. It is also important to realize that Commissioner McMahon had promised the British support to Sharif Ali for the creation of an Arab kingdom and based on this promise, Sharif Ali started the revolt against the OE in 1916. In this case, the British government had sold the same territory twice. On one hand, they had given the Sharif the assurance that they would support the creation of an Arab kingdom. On the other hand, they had promised the British support for the establishment of a Jewish state in the same land where Sharif Ali meant to create his kingdom. This way of negotiating has led to an atmosphere of mistrust, as it made the Arabs believe that the Western World was not by their side. This dishonest way of policy making not only complicated the situation after the war but it damaged so deeply the roots of the IR in the ME that even today the consequences can easily be seen.

2.5 The Colonial Time in the ME

After WWI most of the ME countries were under the administration of English or French. There were only few countries that did survive the European colonization. “Turkish nationalists rallied around General Mustafa Kemal (later known as ‘Ataturk’) in opposing the draconian terms of the Paris Peace Conference, culminating in the Treaty of Sevres (August 1920) that reduced the Ottoman Empire to a rump state combining parts of northern and western Anatolia with Istanbul as its capital.”³⁵ As a result of the 1921-22 war, the Turkish nationalists succeeded in declaring Turkey an independent country, one year after, it gained recognition in the Treaty of Lausanne.

34 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 46.

35 *Ibid.*, 52.

The Iranian nationalists strongly opposed the efforts of the British government to create a protectorate in 1919. “In 1921, the commander of the Iranian Cossack Brigade, Reza Khan, led a coup that brought down the Qajar dynasty and gave rise to the Pahlavi state that would rule Iran until the Islamic Revolution in 1979.”³⁶ Abdul Aziz Al Saud with his forces “succeeded in uniting the Arabian Peninsula from the Persian Gulf to the Hijaz Province on the Red Sea by 1924.”³⁷ As a result of this event Abdul Aziz Al Saud was recognized by Britain as King of the Hejaz and Nejd, and in 1932 this kingdom was renamed Saudi Arabia.

Following the independence of Turkey the nationalist Turks were determined to build their state in accordance with Westphalian principles. They abandoned the caliphate institutions because they were pursuing national interests and not the concept of universalism. “Henceforth the Muslim world was stranded between the victorious Westphalian international order and the now-unrealizable concept of dar al-Islam. With scant experience, the societies of the Middle East set out to redefine themselves as modern states, within borders that for the most part had no historical roots.”³⁸ Affairs occurred in this manner and provided sufficient material for the radical ideologues in the ME to manipulate the Arab people against our international system. After WWI, the Arab provinces that used to be under the Ottoman administration were not portioned in accordance with the people’s will. These provinces were colonized because the two GP (Britain and France) considered the Arab communities living there as not ready to be self-governed. The Arab communities were restrained in experimenting with governing systems and finding the ones that best fits their needs. They were restrained to try and find out that universalism is outdated and unrealizable concept.

2.5.1 Arab Aspirations for a Single Nation

In spite of the fact that it was considered to be an imposed and foreign system the new Arab states began to adapt to the international order. What these newly born states demanded from the international community at that time was “their peoples’ right to join as equal members”³⁹ and not a variety of pluralist states as had happened in the

36 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 52.

37 Ibid., 52.

38 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 112-113.

39 Ibid., 113.

continent of Europe after a thirty-year war. They were constantly pushing for a supra-national identity “based on a range of greater Arab nations transcending the colonial boundaries.”⁴⁰ Two versions emerged because of this and both were against pluralism values. The first version, could be accounted for its Wesphalian elements and became known as Pan-Arabism concept. The state they were looking to form was a “united Arab nation, a single ethnic, linguistic, and cultural entity.”⁴¹ This version was not accepted by the GP due to the fact that it was aiming to exceed the colonial partitions. Therefore, it was against what the GP had planned for. The second version which later became known as Muslim Brotherhood was also demanding to form a nation that would exceed the colonial boundaries and use Islamic religion as a pretext for a national identity. “Many considered Islamism as a way to join the postwar era without having to abandon their values, to be modern without having to become Western.”⁴² This version was also refused because it was against the pluralism values based on which international order was founded and also it was against the GP’ intentions.

Amir Faisal, who later became the King of Syria, had agreed in Versailles Conference to support the Balfour Declaration so that the GP would support in return his movement for the creation of the Arab Kingdom. On February 6, 1919 Faisal presented a memorandum to the Supreme Council of the Paris Peace Conference demanding “to unite the Arabs eventually into one nation.”⁴³ Regardless of ethnic and linguistic similarities, Faisal was well aware that there were large socio-economic differences in the Arab world. Therefore, he did not wish that all Arab communities be included in a single state. “He sought immediate and full independence for Greater Syria (including Lebanon, Syria, and Transjordan) and the western Arabian province of Hijaz; he accepted foreign intervention in Palestine to mediate between Jewish and Arab demands, and in Mesopotamia, where Britain had declared its interests in oil fields; and he declared the Yemen and the central Arabian province of Najd outside the scope of the Arab kingdom.”⁴⁴ Faisal stated that the GP should not hesitate to help the Arab people toward unification:

“In our opinion, if our independence be conceded and our local competence established, the natural influences of race, language, and interest will soon draw us into one people ... To achieve this [the great powers] must lay aside the thought of individual profits,

40 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 52.

41 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 113.

42 Ibid., 113.

43 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 48.

44 Ibid., 48.

and of their old jealousies. In a word, we ask you not to force your whole civilization upon us, but to help us to pick out what serves us from your experience. In return we can offer you little but gratitude. (Hurewitz 1979: 130-2)⁴⁵

Even this proposal was not taken into consideration by the GP due to the simple reason that it was against the Sykes-Picot agreement. Considering the demands of the Syrian people for self-government, Woodrow Wilson (President of the US) had proposed to send a commission in order to measure the public opinion in Syria.

2.5.2 The King-Crane Commission

President Wilson had appointed Henry Churchill King (president of Oberlin College) and Charles R. Crane (a businessman from Chicago) in the position of commissioners. In May 1919 the two American appointees left for Syria in order to meet with the local representatives and conduct a report measuring the aspirations of the Arab people. “The Commission arrived in Jaffa on 10 June, and spent six weeks touring Syria and Palestine. It held meetings in more than forty towns and rural centres, and collected more than 1,800 petitions.”⁴⁶ Even though the King-Crane report was published late because the scheme for the partition of the ME was already finished by the GP, the commission itself turned out to be successful in measuring the Arab people’s opinion regarding the post-war partition of their lands. The main findings of this report clearly underlined the aspirations of the Syrian people for independence, which they sought to achieve under a short-term American or British mandate. “Syria, including Palestine, should be established as a single monarchy under Faisal’s rule, with Lebanon given extensive autonomy within the Syrian state.”⁴⁷

Another important finding of the commission is that a great number of Arab people opposed the formation of a Jewish state in Palestine. “King and Crane called for major restrictions in Zionist settlement in Palestine, noting that ‘more than 72 per cent—1,350 in all—of all the petitions in the whole of Syria were directed against the Zionist program’ (Hurewitz 1979: 196).”⁴⁸ In spite of the fact that the King-Crane report had given a clear reflection of the Arabic opinion, showing that they were strongly against the Sykes-Picot Agreement and the Balfour Declaration, this report did not have any effect on the post-war partition plans of the ME. We can not blame the Arab’s lack of

45 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 48.

46 *Ibid.*, 49.

47 *Ibid.*, 49.

48 *Ibid.*, 49.

diplomatic experience in IR at all. Since it can be concluded that the GP had considered far more the national interests than the liberal approach that was proposed by President Wilson. The Arab lands in the ME were not partitioned in accordance with the Arab peoples' will but in accordance with GP's will because they were the dominant actors in IR and unluckily they treated these lands as spoils of war.

2.5.3 ME after WWII

From the collapse of the OE until the WWII, the ME region was mainly dominated by Britain and France. However, after the WWII, the mandating powers were exhausted by the war, while the demands of the Arab communities for self-governance were constantly increasing. "In the 1950s and 1960s, the more or less feudal and monarchical governments in Egypt, Iraq, Syria, Yemen and Libya were overthrown by their military leaders, who proceeded to establish secular governance."⁴⁹ As a method to gain popular support, military leaders turned to nationalism. From 1954 to 1970, Egypt was ruled by Gamal Abdel Nasser and after him, Anwar al-Sadat ruled with great popular support. In the same way, for more than three decades, Iraq was ruled by a military dictator, Saddam Hussein, who was known for his brutal regime. Although this form of government could be aligned to some extent with the our international order due to the state-based system these autocratic regimes were deeply against human rights and democratic values which resulted in a vast popular dissatisfaction.

The dictatorships could not manage to undermine the Islamic heritage in the Arab world and soon it appeared on the surface as a neglected obligation. "Islamist parties merging a critique of the excesses and failures of the secular rulers with scriptural arguments about the need for divinely inspired governance advocated the formation of a pan-Islamic theocracy superseding the existing states."⁵⁰ The Islamic Parties accused the military leaders that they had left behind their religious obligation which leads to the unification of the Arab world. But also, the autocrats responded to these accusations in a cruel manner by "suppressing Islamist political movements, which they charged with undermining modernization and national unity."⁵¹ As a consequence of these two extreme approaches the conditions for a proper development of the civil society were suppressed, leaving little hope for political reforms in the near future.

49 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 113.

50 Ibid., 114.

51 Ibid., 114.

2.6 The CW Impact in the ME

The Soviet Union's (SU) inclusion in the WWII in June 1941 was undoubtedly one of the major factors that led to victory. However, this crucial contribution also had some negative results. Competing to become the most dominant actors in the world, both superpowers SU and US had put to much efforts in spreading their influences across the globe, also known as ideological rivalry. This rivalry between the two superpowers had begun during the WWII. However it only became visible after the end of this destructive war. The SU sought to spread its communism system to other countries. This socialism version was offering a system of governance where everything is owned and controlled by the state and where there are no class divisions because everyone is treated equally. While the US sought to spread its democratic system to other countries. This capitalism version was offering a free world where people can compete with each other and it considered communism as imposing system. In the spring of 1947, the US announced Truman Doctrine, expressing the US determination to support the countries threatened by communism. Some of President Truman's words:

*“One of the primary objectives of the foreign policy of the United States is the creation of conditions in which we and other nations will be able to work out a way of life free from coercion ... We shall not realize our objectives, however, unless we are willing to help free peoples to maintain their free institutions and their national integrity against aggressive movements that seek to impose upon them totalitarian regimes. This is no more than a frank recognition that totalitarian regimes imposed on free peoples, by direct or indirect aggression, undermine the foundations of international peace and hence the security of the United States.”*⁵²

After the WWII, for the European mandate powers it became almost impossible to keep order in the ME because they were militarily and economically drained from the warfare, while the Arabs's demands for self-governing was constantly growing. The SU and US found themselves under the obligation to extend their influences in the ME region. Some of the main reasons to spread the influences in the region were, “first, the desires of the superpowers to gain strategic advantage in the region given the departure, or

52 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 65.

imminent departure, of Britain and France, second, the fact that the region contained some two-thirds of the world's oil reserves in a context in which oil was becoming increasingly vital to the economy of the Western world, and, third, the fact that, in a novel way that made it quite distinct from previous power struggles, the CW represented an ideological conflict between two very different political, social, and economic systems."⁵³ A point that is often overlooked is the fact that in this region there happened to be two-thirds of oil reserves in the world. Therefore, it can be concluded that the oil factor in the ME was much more important than the ideological rivalry between the two superpowers. "By the mid-to-late 1940s, US oil companies controlled at least 42 per cent of Middle Eastern oil, as well, of course, as having majority interests in companies nearer home (in Mexico and Venezuela, and in the US itself)."⁵⁴ The ME continues to be considered a very strategic region by the Western world because even today the Western militaries and industries depend heavily on its oil sources.

2.6.1 The Relations of the Superpowers with the ME

The situation in the region would be much easier if one or both of the Superpowers of the CW could exercise total control over the actions of the ME countries or, at least, if they could influence them to stop or undo actions already undertaken. The relations between the two superpowers and the ME countries during the CW were fragile and vague. For example, "the US and the SU were unable to prevent Israel and Egypt going to war in 1967 (Tibi 1998: 65); in 1980, Iraq did not inform the SU of its intention to invade Iran until the invasion had taken place (which resulted in Soviet exasperation, expressed in the form of a temporary stoppage of arms deliveries)."⁵⁵ Scholars have noted such cases when ME countries tried and sometimes succeeded in taking advantage of the rivalry between the two superpowers during the CW. "An obvious example here was the willingness of the SU to finance the Aswan Dam when the United States would no longer support the project, because Egypt had bought or ordered arms from the SU."⁵⁶ The US was concerned of a such scenario, where Arabs could buy sophisticated arms from the Russian rivals and, then seek to defeat Israel with military supremacy.

53 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 64.

54 *Ibid.*, 67.

55 *Ibid.*, 63.

56 *Ibid.*, 71.

2.6.2 The Rivalry of the Superpowers in the ME

The CW can not be labeled as the only cause for the anarchic situation in the ME, the rivalry between the two superpowers had a negative effect in the Arab world and it definitely hampered the political development in ME countries. The fact that during the CW the ME countries were allied with one or the other superpower and that they followed state-based principles can not be denied. These countries did not support the policies of the superpowers according to their free will because both ideologies had not risen in the Arab world but were imposed by the East and West. It is therefore best to emphasize that the ME countries were supported by one or the other superpower due to ideological reasons. “Egypt, Syria, Algeria and Iraq generally supported Soviet policies and followed the Soviet lead. Jordan, Saudi Arabia, Iran, and Morocco were friendly to the United States and were relying on U.S. support for their security.”⁵⁷ Even when there was a political development such as parliamentary elections in the region, they were quickly overwhelmed by fundamentally non-democratic groups. Such initiatives were accused for being friendly with one or the other superpower and so they did not survive the CW era.

Fearing that one might take control of the ME, the mentality of the superpowers was to destroy whatever the opponent builds, which lead to long-lasting consequences in the region. “In the inter-war and immediately post-war period, there were lively and contested parliamentary elections in Iran, Iraq, and Syria, and perhaps also in Egypt. Part of—perhaps most of—what killed this off in the 1950s was the pressure of the Cold War.”⁵⁸ The rivalry between the two superpowers during the CW has negatively affected the region by deepening the old internal tensions in the Arab world and also creating new tensions that did not exist before.

In the Arab world the establishment of a new government did not mean only taking over the competencies of the existing administration but it also meant suppressing the political opponents so they are removed for good from the political scene. “Unfortunately, the nature of the East-West conflict meant that, for example, when the monarchy was restored in Iran after the overthrow of Musaddiq, or the United Arab Republic of Egypt and Syria was set up, or Qasim’s regime was overthrown in Iraq, such events were followed by round-up

57 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 115.

58 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 74.

and imprisonment, torture, and (especially in Iraq in 1963) the execution of thousands of local communists and leftists and their suspected sympathizers.”⁵⁹ This period led to brutal dictators such as Saddam Hussein who remained in power for decades, destroying anyone who had the courage to raise their voice against him. The Islamic Parties were accused for being against national unity and being anti-modernism. While the Communist Parties were suppressed under the justification that they were illegal and damaging, despite the fact that they were state-based parties and not based on ideologies that were in conflict with the international order.

It must be remembered that the ideological conflict between the SU and US was not born in the ME, so the Arab communities understood the CW rivalry nothing more than a hegemonic struggle among the two superpowers. The recently de colonized Arab states were supported by one or the other superpowers because they both wanted to spread their influence in the region. Arabs were friendly to them, not because they liked their ideologies, but because being friendly to them was the only way to get in power. It was noted that during the CW the Islamic and non-Islamic world had a relationship based on Westphalian principles; however even that can not be considered healthy because it was not a free will relationship between the two very different worlds but an imposed one. The CW ended and the Arab world found itself surrounded by four long-lasting problems: (1) The leadership under the brutal dictators who stayed in power for decades without the support of the electorate. (2) Due to the brutal regime, dictators had succeeded in suppressing any opposition voice who called for legitimate government and of course, under those circumstances, people are afraid to start doing opposition. (3) The absence of a reasonable opposition or civil society, created room for Islamic politics. (4) Radical ideologues are using the domestic social problems as a pretext to manipulate the people with the old motto: “the current international order does not work and the only way is Islam”.

2.7 Dependence of the Western World on ME Oil

It did not take long to realize that the ME was becoming a very strategic region due to the large oil reserves found there. “Oil is still a highly strategic energy supply, and MENA—despite US shale extractions—occupies a central position in providing it. OPEC countries command 81 per cent of world oil reserves and Middle East countries account

59 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 75.

for 66 per cent of these (OPEC 2015). Since, contrary to previous optimistic estimates, Caspian Sea oil reserves are equivalent only to those of the North Sea, MENA retains its prime place as the oil-provider excellence.”⁶⁰ Many industrial countries, and especially Western Europe, is heavily dependent on the ME oil reserves. Of course these developed countries would try to gain as easy as possible access to the large oil reserves located in the ME. However, it is important to realize that (especially in the 21st century) not all the efforts of the Western World in the region have to do with the oil. The industrial countries are constantly working to reduce their huge dependency on the Arabian oil through technological developments. The US does not directly depend on the ME oil because it produces its own oil, plus it imports oil from other countries such as Mexico, Venezuela, and Canada.

In recent times, the Western countries have used ME oil more as “a tool, rather than as an objective: witness the American sanctions against Iran, which continue to this day, then Libya (1982-2004), and the UN-imposed sanctions against Iraq (1990-2003).”⁶¹ “The major industrial powers have made their own access to oil more difficult in order to pursue a political priority.”⁶² This is good news because it shows that the major industrial powers are not limited only to the national interests like the GP did after the WWII but they are thinking beyond that. The industrial powers are not looking only for cheap and easy ways to get access to the oil but they are looking to find reasonable deals that would contribute to the good of all.

2.7.1 Dependence of the ME on the Western World

While the industrial countries are working to reduce their dependency on the ME oil; the oil-producing countries of the ME depend almost entirely on the benefits from oil exportation. “On average, Gulf economies rely on oil for over 80 per cent of their national income.”⁶³ The main concern here is that the large benefits from oil exportation has lead to a passive society. The Arab communities in oil-producing countries accept or allow what their governments do, without active response or resistance. Also, these oil-producing countries have failed to create a productive work environment which competes

60 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 84.

61 *Ibid.*, 114.

62 *Ibid.*, 114.

63 *Ibid.*, 84.

with other developed countries. The other concern is that due to the huge dependency of the oil-producing countries on the benefits from oil exports their national security may be threatened if things go wrong. For instance, if the international community decides to impose an embargo on one of these countries, then the national security of that country is directly endangered due to the fact that the income of oil-producing countries heavily depends on oil exports. Also, if the major industrial powers manage to sharply reduce their dependency on the Arabian oil, then the entire regional security of the ME would be endangered. This can be a very unfortunate scenario for the ME because first, it would put an end to the main income of the oil-producing countries; second, it would threaten the regimes who act independently from the society due to the large oil reserves, and third, it can put the entire region into chaos state, where the consequences go beyond state-borders.

2.7.2 Oil as a Paralyzing Source in the Region

One of the major factors that has debilitated the political development in the Arab world is the availability of the large oil reserves in the ME. For example, in developed countries governments try to provide a positive work environment in order to encourage people to work; then in the name of the common good the state imposes taxes upon its citizens. This system causes the government to directly depend on the society. First of all, in order to be legitimate to represent the people, the representatives are chosen by the population through democratic and fair elections. Then, in order to justify the taxation of its citizens, the government must provide them goods, such as public services, security, social welfare, human rights, accountability and so on. Whereas in oil-producing countries of the ME, it is different because the government does not directly depend on the electorate. The governments in the oil-producing countries can cover their finance needs with the income of exporting oil to the other countries, therefore they are called “rentier states”⁶⁴. The governments in oil-producing countries consider themselves to be owners who are capable to finance their needs by exporting oil to other countries in exchange of money, military assets or other favours.

64 The author Louise Fawcett defines the rentier state as follows: In ‘normal’ countries, the state is supported by society and must, in order to pay for itself, establish a system to extract from society part of the surplus that it generates; in oil-exporting countries, the state is paid by the oil rent, which accrues to it directly from the rest of the world, and supports society through the distribution or allocation of this rent, through various mechanisms of rent circulation.
Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 117.

Due to the fact that these oil-exporting governments do not need to impose taxes upon its citizens; they also feel released from the duty of answerability to the citizens. One negative outcome of this is that, many of the oil-producing countries in the ME were ruled by autocrats who forcibly seized power as a result of military coups and the availability of large oil reserves enabled them to stay in power for decades. “The possibility of alternation is essential to democracy: no opposition will remain loyal to democratic institutions if it does not stand a chance of ever winning elections; and no political force will accept a transition to democracy if the first elections are also likely to be the last.”⁶⁵ Large oil reserves made it possible for dictators like Saddam Hysein to rule the country for decades without the support of society. These regimes made the political opposition a very dangerous place for people to join and in that way there was no one left to oppose the government except for the political Islam. Out of this two universalist Islamic-based versions were born: “the Sunni version by way of the regionally extensive Muslim Brotherhood founded in 1928, Hamas, the radical movement that gained power in Gaza in 2007, and the global terrorist movement al-Qaeda; and the Shia version through the Khomeini revolution and its offshoot, the Lebanese “state within a state” Hezbollah. In violent conflict with each other they were united in their commitment to dismantle the existing regional order and rebuild it as a divinely inspired system.”⁶⁶

2.8 Political Islam in the ME

The pressure of the ideological rivalry between the two superpowers during the CW had created a favorable atmosphere for the regimes to remain in power. These brutal regimes had managed to suppress any opposition movement which resulted in dictatorship. Because of this people hesitated to raise their voices against the regimes because they were aware of the dangers. But even if they do so they do not gain a lot of popular support. “What opposition there was drifted into the hands of religious organizations of various kinds, since, in Islamic countries, governments cannot ultimately close down the mosques.”⁶⁷ Realizing the public dissatisfaction with the regimes in the ME, the radical Islamist ideologues started manipulating with the social challenges in the Arab world by pointing the fingers at the fragile order in the region and seeking to replace it with a divine order that is based in Islam.

65 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 119.

66 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 117.

67 Louise Fawcett, *International Relations of the Middle East* (Oxford University Press, 2016), 75.

2.8.1 Muslim Brotherhood

In 1928, an Egyptian religious ideologist named Hassan al-Banna had founded an organization called Muslim Brotherhood. It originated in Egypt and then spread across the region of the ME. This organization was formed as a sign of moral resistance against the foreign influences in the region. Initially al-Banna's organization was a simple meeting place for Muslim believers where they could discuss and comment on various political and social events happening in the region. However, as a result of the increasing domestic dissatisfaction the influence of this organization grew and soon it became an important political organization in the Arab world. After al-Banna became an influential actor in the region, in the year of 1947, he addressed a statement toward Farouk (King of Egypt). He was concerned that Egypt has fallen under the foreign influence. And so, he sought to establish a divine system which is based on the Islamic religion.

*"The West, al-Banna asserted, "which was brilliant by virtue of its scientific perfection for a long time . . . is now bankrupt and in decline. Its foundations are crumbling, and its institutions and guiding principles are falling apart." The Western powers had lost control of their own world order: "Their congresses are failures, their treaties are broken, and their covenants torn to pieces." The League of Nations, intended to keep the peace, was "a phantasm." Though he did not use the terms, al-Banna was arguing that the Westphalian world order had lost both its legitimacy and its power. And he was explicitly announcing that the opportunity to create a new world order based on Islam had arrived. "The Islamic way has been tried before," he argued, and "history has testified as to its soundness." If a society were to dedicate itself to a "complete and all-encompassing" course of restoring the original principles of Islam and building the social order the Quran prescribes, the "Islamic nation in its entirety"—that is, all Muslims globally—"will support us"; "Arab unity" and eventually "Islamic unity" would result."*⁶⁸

Al-Banna, with careful language, was saying that the current international order had failed; and should therefore, be replaced with an Islamic order. He was stating that such order based on Islam would gain the support of all Muslim believers around the globe because "the Islamic way has been tried before ... and history has testified as to its soundness."⁶⁹ If Islam is the only way that this world should obey because it was sent from God, then how come both empires (Islamic and Ottoman) failed

68 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 119.

69 Ibid., 119.

to accomplish the concept of universalism? History best demonstrates that such concept is unattainable. The Islamic order concept is unattainable even for the Arab world itself, never mind the global aims. Every group or organization that has aimed to bring the concept of universalism have been unsuccessful and brought devastating. Such a concept is against the human nature; therefore, even the IE was divided into two doctrines after the death of Prophet Muhammad in 632. For as long as opportunistic actors such as Hassan al-Banna continue to have great influence over the Arab world the ME will be a region in turmoil and not find its peace.

2.8.2 Calls to Replace the World Order

Following the death of al-Banna in 1949, his texts became an inspiration for many extremist ideologues in the Muslim community. They were using al-Banna's ideology as an argument to declare war on our pluralist order. The ideologist of Muslim Brotherhood, Sayyid Qutb, was not so careful in expressing himself like his predecessor al-Banna. On his book titled "Milestones", he openly proclaimed war on the Westphalian international order. According to Qutb's view, the existing states that are practicing the principles of the Westphalian order are illegitimate due to the fact that they were not practicing Islamic-based principles. Therefore, he was demanding to overthrow all of them, in order to install a universal system which would serve all humanity as described in the book of Qur'an. This achievement would ultimately accomplish the early efforts of the IE. "This would complete the process begun by the initial wave of Islamic expansion in the seventh and eighth centuries, which is then to be carried throughout the earth to the whole of mankind, as the object of this religion is all humanity and its sphere of action is the whole earth."⁷⁰

No matter though, how primitive and unrealistic this may sound the world today is challenged with such radical groups who blindly believe this concept and are willing to support it at all costs. "They have been the rallying cry of radicals and jihadists in the Middle East and beyond for decades—echoed by al-Qaeda, Hamas, Hezbollah, the Taliban, Iran's clerical regime, Hizb ut-Tahrir (the Party of Liberation, active in the West and openly advocating the reestablishment of the caliphate in a world dominated by Islam), Nigeria's Boko Haram, Syria's extremist militia Jabhat al-Nusrah, and the Islamic State of Iraq and the Levant, which erupted in a major military assault in mid-2014."⁷¹

70 Henry Kissinger, *World Order* (Penguin Books, 2015), 121.

71 *Ibid.*, 121-122.

In conclusion, the ME seems like a region that has not yet passed the period of ideological clashes. It was restrained to experiment independently by the GP and so, therefore, had someone else to blame for any unpleasant situation in the region. But also, following the de colonization period, the political development of the ME failed due to brutal dictators who did not want to hand the power to someone else. In absence of political parties to oppose the actions of regimes the opposition was left in the hands of radical religious organizations who openly proclaim war on our international order, seeking to install the one of their own which is based on Islamic principles. This is not a dangerous concept only for the Arab world itself but also for the international security, especially when it is supported with VA of terrorism. Moreover, the cries to overthrow the current international system and replace it with an Islamic-based one means that the Arab world is against the world. Therefore, for as long as individuals like al-banna and Qutb continue to be important actors in the Arab world the region of the ME will not be able to take its destiny into its own hands.

3 Terrorism

The beginning of this paper stated that terrorism is not something new for mankind because, even in the past, terrorist tactics were used by different groups or tribes for different reasons. It was also pointed out that it is wrong to think that terrorism comes exclusively from Islam or ME because many scholars demonstrate cases where other religions were involved in terrorist activities as well. Also, terrorism does not necessarily derive only from religion because VA of terrorism can be done on different basis, such as “religious, ethnic or nationalist, and ideological”⁷². Today, though, it seems that Islamic terrorism is one of the most pressing issues that has lead to some of the main international security threats. If an ethnic group commits VA of terrorism because they demand specific or equal rights, then those rights can be granted. If a nation uses VA of terrorism because they seek autonomy or independence from an aggressive country, it can also be achieved with the support of the International Community (IC). However, when a state, organization or a group is seeking to overthrow the entire international order, in order to replace it with a religious-based order, in this case no compromise can be reached. Therefore, it is important that states individually and collectively take the right measures to in order protect themselves from VA of terrorism. At least until the deep-seated influence of religious ideologues that support the concept of universalism in the region is extinguished. For the moment it seems that the Arab world has neither the will nor the urge to overcome this situation. How long should we wait to see a political development that allows the Arab world to live in peace with itself and the outside world? Unfortunately the ME looks like a region that is struggling to find a balance and it is not expected that this balance will be found soon. They are not capable to install a proper order that allows the inner Arab world to live in peace. Yet, they seek to overthrow our international order because they believe that it should be replaced with an order that belonged to the 7th century.

3.1 The Challenges of Contemporary Terrorism

Technology is advancing rapidly today and the spread of news or information is a matter of seconds. The media constantly informs us how both national security of many countries and the international security is endangered as a result of VA of terrorism.

72 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 278.

Apparently terrorism is a rising phenomenon and it has never been more challenging to fight. If in the past a terrorist organization was considered a threat to the national security of one country, then today many terrorist groups or organizations pose a threat to the national security of many countries. Therefore, it is essential to be accurately informed about terrorism in order to fight it with the right methods. Democratic societies should not fall into wrong conclusions like “Islam is a religion of terrorists” because such discriminative description can lead to consequences like the abuse of human rights. And if someone’s rights are denied just because he or she belongs to a certain religion, then terrorism has won. The most unforgettable and devastating terrorist attacks, such as 9/11 in the US, the continuing VA in the ME that often don’t get attention, and the frequent terror attacks that we are seeing lately happening in Europe demonstrate that we cannot sit back and wait for miracles. Today, more than ever before, it is essential that the authorities of every country, community, organization or corporation cooperate collectively in order to prevent the dangers that come from terrorism. It is understandable to have different theories and approaches among researchers about the definition of terrorism because not all societies are challenged in the same way. However, we all agree that terrorism is a growing phenomenon against which we must work together to stop its violent storm and, hopefully eradicate it from our midst.

3.1.1 Different Measures in Different Countries

When dealing with terrorism, it is essential to choose the right measures because not all countries are challenged in the same way. Measurements that work in one place may not be effective in another. Peter J. Katzenstein argues that “the attack on the World Trade Center and the Pentagon is like a strong beam of light that gets filtered by national lenses, of different self-conceptions and institutional practices, which create distinctive political responses that will test severely alliance cohesion in the years to come.”⁷³ Countries choose counterterrorism policies based on how they conceive “the use of violence, how publics perceive and interpret insecurity, and how threats are constructed politically.”⁷⁴ For instance, before the 9/11 attacks, the US used to treat domestic terrorism as crime. However, due to huge casualties and due to the fact that it was attacked by a terrorist organization that operated outside its territory, for the US “the September 11 attack was an act

73 Peter J. Katzenstein, *Same War-Different Views: Germany, Japan, and Counterterrorism*, (The International Organization Foundation, 2003), 732.

74 *Ibid.*, 734.

of “war” that required and justified, foremost, a response by the U.S. military.”⁷⁵ Although some of the closest allies joined the US war on terrorism; they did not join it with the same state of mind as the US because their counterterrorism policies differed and some of them were facing strong opposition at home.

3.2 Definition of Terrorism

This paper has mentioned often that the phenomenon of terrorism has been present in the world for centuries. Different groups had supported their causes by committing VA of terrorism for different political and religious purposes. Considering the fact that terrorism is an old phenomenon, it indicates that terrorism has emerged in various ways and techniques throughout the centuries. Each time adapting to the changing environment. A long time ago the Assassins⁷⁶ used to send their suicidal killer to eliminate individuals that were considered as enemies. Today, groups or organizations like Al-Qaeda use a variety of techniques such as “bombings, kidnappings, assaults including assassinations, and takeovers of buildings, planes, or ships, invariably with hostages.”⁷⁷ This shows that terrorist groups change their attacking techniques in order to be unpredictable and hard to prevent. Because of the changing nature of terrorism there are various theories and standpoints about it. And so countries and the international organizations are struggling to find a definition that serves all of us. Important to policy makers around the world, is to include definition of terrorism in their criminal code so that they can arrest and punish the individuals involved in activities related to terrorism. The following is broadly accepted, and is formed by six elements. “Terrorism involves (1) the use of violence or threat of violence (2) by an organized group (3) to achieve political objectives. The violence (4) is directed against a target audience that extends beyond the immediate victims, who are

75 Peter J. Katzenstein, *Same War-Different Views: Germany, Japan, and Counterterrorism*, (The International Organization Foundation, 2003), 732.

76 The Assassins was a radical Muslim group of the Shiite branch of Islam operated in the eleventh-thirteenth centuries, from 1090 to 1270, in the northern part of modern Iran and the Levant. This order is known more for its notorious acts of assassination than for any other things, which was the assassination of prominent personalities who were often Muslims but sometimes Christians in the position of power, and assassination of ordinary people too. The assassination acts were suicidal in the sense that the Assassins were certain that there would be no return from the mission; the murder act they carried out led to their own death as well. But this was what they wanted as they were brain-washed to believe that suicide assassination was a short and definite path to Paradise. The Assassins were destroyed by the Mongols after a power struggle. The Mongols believed that the Assassins would pose a real threat to them and they were convinced that their extermination was necessary. **Source:** Salam Abdulrahman, *The Assassins: ancestors of modern Muslim suicide bombers?*, (Journal of University of Human Development, 2016), 400.

77 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 276.

often innocent civilians. Further (5), while a government can be either the perpetrator of violence or the target, it is considered an act of terrorism only if one or both actors is not a government. Finally, (6) terrorism is a weapon of the weak (Lutz and Lutz 2008: 9).⁷⁸ Even this definition does not include all VA that are considered to be terrorism. For instance, lately it is noted that some individuals are committing VA of terrorism (including citizens of democratic countries) without having specific instructions or being recruited by any terrorist group or organization. In addition, the aforementioned definition does not include individuals who got radicalized and committed VA of terrorism as a result of terror campaigns that can easily be found on the internet. The sixth element of this definition correctly points out that terrorism is a weapon of the weak. As an illustration, terrorist organizations are not capable to install their religion-based order in the region of ME because of dictatorial leaderships. Due to the fact that they cannot win against authoritarianism they decided to support their causes with VA of terrorism. Moreover, terrorist organizations such as Al-Qaeda and ISIS are incapable to replace our international order with an universal Islamic order based on the Qur'an's book; and so they turned to terrorism by attacking countries internationally.

3.2.1 Intentions and Methods of Terrorism

Although anyone can become a victim of this phenomenon terrorists intend to attack officials in order to generate fear in mass. For instance, terrorist targets can be “members of the elite, supporters of the government, members of a particular ethnic or religious community, or the general public.”⁷⁹ However, while attacks on public institutions are occurring more rarely due to increased security measures, attacks on places where a large number of civilians can get killed or injured are occurring more frequently. It is often reported that terrorists committed VA by attacking places with large crowds such as sport stadiums, squares, tourist sites, concerts, shopping malls and so on. Some of the preferred techniques used recently by terrorists are the suicide vest or car bombs. Suicidal terrorists that use those bombing techniques will make sure that they are surrounded by a large number of people before they detonate their devices. The suicidal attacks in crowded places are used mainly for four reasons: (1) because civilians are usually unprepared, (2) one can hit a large number of people, (3) surveillance of suspected terrorists is difficult because of the large number of people, and (4) in crowded places, the generating fear effects will be much higher.

78 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 275.

79 *Ibid.*, 276.

Terrorist groups or individuals can commit VA of terrorism based on two reasons. One method is to justify their actions in the name of universalism concept of jihad. In other words, they claim that our world order has failed because it was not founded based on Islamic principles; therefore it should be replaced. Terrorist organizations may be well aware that our international order cannot be overthrown by committing VA of terrorism. However, it seems that the main idea of terrorist attacks is to challenge this system created in Europe by making it difficult to live in peace. Another method of terrorist attacks can be seen as an objection against Western influence in the Arab world. They use such acts as a sign of protest, demanding to remove or at least to minimize the foreign influences. For instance, terrorists can attack countries based on the misconception that “they are damaging our culture; therefore, we will damage their culture”. Absolutely both of the concepts are wrong. Moreover, having in mind that terrorist groups have a variety of techniques they can use for several purposes; “perhaps the greatest danger in the future is that a suicide attack might be combined with the use of biological, chemical, or radiological weapons.”⁸⁰ In fact, if the weapons of mass destruction are used by any country in a situation when war has been declared, the consequences would be far too devastating. Considering the fact that, the aim of terrorists is to kill or injure as many people as possible, they would not hesitate to use such weapons at all.

3.3 The Spread of Terrorism

The statistics in the XXI century best demonstrate that terrorism is a growing phenomenon that is repeatedly threatening and challenging both national and international security. Even though domestic terrorist attacks have always been more common the number of international terrorist attacks have also increased due to bigger media coverage. Brian M. Jenkins described international terrorism in this way: “International terrorism may be defined as acts of violence or campaigns of violence waged outside the accepted rules and procedures of international diplomacy and war. Breaking the rules may include attacking diplomats and other internationally protected persons, attacking international travel and commerce, or exporting violence by various means to nations that normally would not, under the traditional rules, be considered participants in the local conflict.”⁸¹

80 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 277.

81 Brian M. Jenkins, *International Terrorism: A New Kind of Warfare*, (Santa Monica: The Rand Corporation, 1974), 2.

When it comes to VA of terrorism with jihadist background, all of these incidents can be labeled as international terrorist attacks because it is known that such terrorist organizations declare war on our international order. To better understand why terrorism is considered as one of the main threats to the national security of many countries, see the data in the table below.

Table 3.1: Terrorist fatalities, by region, 1998 - 2010⁸²

Year	Region							Total	
	Africa	Africa	Asia ¹	Eastern Europe ²	Latin America	Europe	Middle East		North America ³
1998		1526	1336	168	600	48	995	5	4678
1999		784	666	454	235	11	562	5	2717
2000		649	1383	231	209	30	310	0	2812
2001		782	1080	238	243	29	632	3004	6008
2002		90	1153	379	251	9	906	3	2991
2003		320	995	283	183	5	844	2	2632
2004		271	1746	634	120	195	2134	0	5100
2005		368	1393	102	132	58	3447	2	5502
2006		910	2882	50	112	4	4712	8	8678
2007		1196	3378	41	71	78	8754	24	13542
2008		555	2219	66	42	1	2305	15	5203
2009		430	2260	88	8	10	1782	3	4581
2010		378	2004	162	4	5	1257	3	3813

The exact number of fatalities occurring in some attacks is unknown.

¹ Includes Australasia and the Pacific islands.

² Former communist countries of Eastern Europe and successor states of the Soviet Union in Europe and Asia.

³ United States, Canada and Mexico.

Source: Start (2011)

3.3.1 Causes of Terrorism

There are several factors that push individuals toward terrorism. Based on the motives that they use to commit VA, terrorism can be categorized as: “are religious, ethnic or nationalist, and ideological.”⁸³ To put it another way, “individuals in a society become so discontented or frustrated with their inability to bring about what they see as necessary changes since other means of seeking change have failed that they resort to violence.”⁸⁴ Speaking of terrorist organizations with jihadist concept, the freshest example that we can use is ISIS. This terrorist organization grew rapidly by merging with other terrorist groups in the ME who support the same concept of creating an universal Islamic order. As a result of the ongoing ISIS recruiting campaigns conducted in social media a large number of radicalized people from every continent of the world traveled to the ME in order to join the terrorist armed groups. Different terrorist groups merged into a single organization, trying to prove the old concept of universalism by proclaiming war on our international order. But anyone who has little knowledge of any religion, can easily tell that this organization is anything else but religious. As a result of a successful cooperation between Western armies this terrorist organization is being defeated and is losing the majority of the large territory that it dominated. Now that it has been proven that universalism is an inexcusable concept and that jihad is a warlike strategy, groups and individuals who support this concept will remain dissatisfied and may resort to VA of terrorism.

3.3.2 Terrorism as a Factor in ME

Within this entire discussion one question arises: How is it possible that terrorism became a factor in a region that is known for its dictatorial leaders who would use their power to suppress any political opposition that questions about their ruling legitimacy? In part the answer to this question was elaborated in the second chapter of this paper. In order to maintain political supremacy and stability, the regime ruled by a single dictator, suppressed any political opponent that dared to call for share of power. Under those circumstances, the hopes for any political party that could challenge the ruling party were shattered and, as a result, the opposition was left in the hands of religious ideologues. While the social dissatisfaction was enormous, the radicalized groups were moved to so-called gray areas where the regime had little control or interest. In this way terrorist groups created their network away

83 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 278.

84 *Ibid.*, 281.

from the regime and once these regimes were weakened or overwhelmed they quickly became a factor in the ME. It is important to point out that terrorism, just like organized crime, exerts its activities in fragile or failed states because in such conditions governments are powerless to extend control over their territory. Moreover, funding criminal activities, getting weapons and operating criminal activities are easier due to corruption and the lack of rule of law.

3.3.3 The Holes of Democracy

It seems that the terrorists have managed to use the achievements of globalization for their own goals. We often see how terrorist organizations use the media as an instrument to frighten the world by giving threatening messages. These groups or organizations use the Internet for recruitment purposes by calling new members to join their “holy war,” what is known as the “radicalization campaigns”. Also, the advancements of technology have made it easier for terrorists to communicate and travel. Because of the communications achievements they can quickly coordinate their actions, commit VA of terrorism then disappear (if not suicidal attacks) without being noticed or caught by the authorities.

It is also important to mention that terrorists take advantage of human rights that are granted in democratic societies such as freedom of thought and speech. Due to the human rights the prevention of terrorist activities is sometimes hard because there are rules and restrictions that must be respected while investigating and gathering information related to terrorism. Even if the authorities manage to arrest these individuals involved in terrorism activities, they can get released if there is no convincing evidence that they committed a crime. In other words, the rights and conditions that civilized societies consider as democratic values, such as freedom of speech, thought and belief may be misused by terrorists. Some researchers see the phenomenon of terrorism as a “reaction to globalization.”⁸⁵ Communities that adhere their religion or tradition in a strict way may feel endangered by the influence that comes from globalization. “Secular globalization also leads to religious and ethnic fragmentation (Ramakrishna and Tan 2003: 3–4). Many religious groups (Christian, Jewish, Muslim, Hindu) are opposed to the secularism that comes with modernity (Pillar 2001: 65).”⁸⁶ Therefore, different religious doctrines consider globalization as rising phenomenon that can diminish or ruin their role in communities where they belong.

85 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 281.

86 *Ibid.*, 281-282.

Especially in religious communities that are too strict and conservative, the reaction to globalization is much harsher. It is important to realize that terrorism does not come as a consequence of a single cause but as combination of several factors. Therefore, when dealing with terrorism is necessary to consider all the possible factors that cause terrorism, instead of focusing in a single factor.

3.4 Prevention: Terrorism as War, Crime, or Disease?

While many countries are alarmed by the dangers that terrorism poses in this century, not all governments choose the same measures to deal with it. When it came to dealing with 9/11 attacks, “Germany has relied on its relatively active counterterrorist policy and involvement in strong multilateral institutions, while Japan has relied on its relatively passive policy and predilection for bilateral deals.”⁸⁷ Although both countries are close allies of the US, the approach was not the same because of the past “institutional norms expressing conceptions of self and other and standards of appropriate behavior.”⁸⁸ In addition, due to the changing nature of terrorism, preventing it is difficult. This implies that if a method that has worked in one country to deal with terrorism it does not necessarily work in another country. Also, having in mind that terrorists are continuously advancing their techniques, measures that have helped in the past to prevent VA of terrorism may not be as effective today. Knowing that terrorism is a weapon of the weak which appears in different violent forms requires a combination of a short-term and long-term measures in order to have effective results.

Scholars around the world have different opinions when it comes to how to deal with terrorism. For all their opinions there are causes and arguments where scholars can relate and often they inform or assist each other. However, in this paper a theory proposed by Peter Sederberg will be used. Sederberg argues that this phenomenon can be seen in three ways. “Terrorism can be viewed as a problem to be resolved by military means (war on terrorism), by normal police techniques (terrorism as crime), or as a medical problem with underlying causes and symptoms (terrorism as disease).”⁸⁹ Therefore, depending on which of these three perspectives governments use to view terrorism, they compose security policies and choose the measurements to deal with it.

87 Peter J. Katzenstein, *Same War-Different Views: Germany, Japan, and Counterterrorism*, (The International Organization Foundation, 2003), 736.

88 *Ibid.*, 736.

89 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 275.

3.4.1 Treating Terrorism as War

In the 21st century, many countries decided to fight terrorism with the analogy of war. The 9/11 coordinated terrorist attacks on the twin towers in New York City and Pentagon that killed 2,973 people and over 6,000 got injured⁹⁰ made the policy makers of many countries to switch sight, shifting from treating terrorism as a crime into war on terrorism. Because it was attacked by a terrorist organization located outside its territory and because of its massive casualties, it was expected that US would respond to this event with military means (war on terrorism). One of the reasons for doing so, as Peter Katzenstein argues, “War, for the United States, is a response that follows quite naturally from a national security policy that had been institutionalized over half a century, during the hot wars in Korea and Vietnam and the cold one with the Soviet Union. With a broad arsenal of sophisticated weapons systems, U.S. security policy had aimed for decades to prevent the recurrence of another surprise attack.”⁹¹ Another reason is that US is the most powerful and most influential country in the world. The asymmetric Al-Qaeda attack on the World Trade Center in New York City were perceived by many policymakers as attack on the entire international system; therefore, it was expected that such event would have an impact in the counterterrorism policies around the globe. For example, “Germany, France, and Australia—like the United Kingdom and the United States—passed new legislation after the events of 9/11, giving government security forces greater powers to detain and interrogate those suspected of terrorism (Haubrick 2003).”⁹²

When countries treat terrorism as a war by confronting it with military activities, this implies that sometimes in a war situation one must choose between the bad alternatives. In other words, in the name of security and stability, some rights and freedoms that are guaranteed in democratic countries can be compromised. For instance, interrogation under torture techniques such as, beating, binding in contorted stress positions, hooding, subjection to deafening noise, sleep disruption, sleep deprivation to the point of hallucination, deprivation of food, drink, and withholding medical care for wounds, as well as waterboarding, walling, sexual humiliation, subjection to extreme heat or extreme cold, confinement in small coffin-like boxes, and repeated slapping can all be justified with the analogy of war.

90 *Nine facts about terrorism in the United States since 9/11*, (*The Washington Post*), <https://www.washingtonpost.com/news/wonk/wp/2013/09/11/nine-facts-about-terrorism-in-the-united-states-since-911/?noredirect=on&utm_term=.dcfa5b55de4d> accessed 12 September 2018

91 Peter J. Katzenstein, *Same War-Different Views: Germany, Japan, and Counterterrorism*, (The International Organization Foundation, 2003), 755.

92 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 285.

Moreover, “Pre-emptive strikes against training facilities or at headquarters, or even the assassinations of key individuals in the terrorist organizations are potential responses.”⁹³ Based on the war analogy, governments are allowed to strike first by using a limited military force against terrorist groups in order to prevent their further action. In this way security forces do not have to wait to be attacked first because such thing is guaranteed if terrorists are not disabled.

3.4.2 Treating Terrorism as Crime

Treating terrorism as a crime by applying regular police methods is one of the most used perspectives in many countries. Before 9/11 attacks, Germany is one example that used to treat its homegrown terrorism during 1970s and 1980s with the analogy of crime. Because of the military consequences during WWII, viewing terrorism with the analogy of war was not an option for a Germany that was determined to learn from the past Nazi mistakes. “In Europe, Germany has been known for its “strong state” approach to counterterrorism. At the same time Germany has had a relatively liberal asylum policy, has extended far-reaching freedoms to religious associations, has imposed strict limitations on the intelligence gathering of the police and other government agencies, and has opposed strongly the death penalty.”⁹⁴ As can be seen, security forces should have waited for terrorists to violate the law and then, based on sufficient evidence, they could be arrested and punished for their wrongdoings. “The ultimate goal of police forces is to deter action by demonstrating that criminals will be caught and punished.”⁹⁵ As an illustration the US also used to treat this phenomenon with police methods. “Terrorists were caught (although it took time in some cases) and brought to trial (although not always convicted). Normal police techniques, including the use of informers and the infiltration of agents into potentially dangerous groups (like the Ku Klux Klan in the United States in the 1960s), drew upon conventional practices.”⁹⁶ However, following the 9/11 tragedy, this approach to terrorism changed not only in the US but in many other countries. Police methods were considered too restrictive to fight against terrorist organizations as big as Al Qaeda or ISIS. Therefore, it was necessary for the governments of many countries to give their security forces greater power when dealing with such dangerous organizations.

93 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 283.

94 Peter J. Katzenstein, *Same War-Different Views: Germany, Japan, and Counterterrorism*, (The International Organization Foundation, 2003), 740-741.

95 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 283.

96 *Ibid.*, 275.

In order to show commitment in international activities and solidarity with the US, “on 11 October 2001 Chancellor Gerhard Schröder declared Germany’s “unrestricted solidarity” with the United States and committed Germany to military operations in defense of freedom and human rights, and for the restoration of stability and security.”⁹⁷ Despite strong domestic opposition, Germany decided to deploy “3,900 German troops as part of U.S.-led coalition fighting the Taliban in Afghanistan.”⁹⁸ Aiming to broaden the scope of the security forces at home, German parliament adopted two laws that served well to counter domestic terrorism. “Membership in, and the assistance, beyond verbal support, of a terrorist organization operating abroad became a criminal offense. This was the legal instrument that allowed the German police to launch efforts to arrest foreign terrorists operating from Germany.”⁹⁹

In fact, after the 9/11 tragedy, the liberal asylum policy, far-reaching religious associations and strict limitations on intelligence gathering were compromised in the name of domestic and international security. “The law, which became effective on 1 January 2002, gave Germany’s various security organizations the power to access the telephone, banking, employment, and university records of individuals.”¹⁰⁰ Moreover, “Germany’s immigration laws also have been rewritten to further enhance information on foreigners, including voice recordings of asylum seekers to be stored for a decade, and online access of the police to the data of the immigration and naturalization services.”¹⁰¹ To summarize, the 9/11 attacks on the World Trade Center had a considerable impact on counterterrorism policies among US allies. It resulted in closer co-operation between security agencies around the world and in better sharing intelligence regarding terrorism. If such attacks did not make the rest of the world view terrorism with the war analogy like in the US, it certainly changed the institutional norms of many countries. Even those countries that still view terrorism as a crime have granted their security forces a wider scope to prevent the dangers that come from this phenomenon. Such a scope remains the same, even after nearly two decades since the 9/11 tragedy.

97 Peter J. Katzenstein, *Same War-Different Views: Germany, Japan, and Counterterrorism*, (The International Organization Foundation, 2003), 748.

98 *Ibid.*, 748.

99 *Ibid.*, 750.

100 *Ibid.*, 750.

101 *Ibid.*, 750.

3.4.3 Treating Terrorism as Disease

Whereas the analogy of war and crime can be considered as short-term reaction concepts, treating terrorism as a disease can be considered as a constructive approach that requires more time. Japan is one example that used to treat terrorism as crisis problem. “Compared with the United States, “Japan is more methodical, less willing to create alarm by preparing for crisis, more sympathetic to the root causes of terrorism, and less willing to respond to terrorism as a global problem.”¹⁰² When the government was faced with homegrown terrorism during 1970s and 1980s, it addressed the problem “by pushing Japan’s terrorists abroad.”¹⁰³ Having them kicked outside the territory of Japan, when terrorists high-jacked planes and kidnapped passengers, “the Japanese government’s initial response was complacency.”¹⁰⁴ However this methodology did not turn out to be successful due to the narrow scope of Japan’s security forces to deal with terrorism. “Despite the shock of the 1995 sarin attack and the policy initiatives taken since then, the Japanese police and system of government still suffers from serious limitations in its organizational and intelligence capabilities.”¹⁰⁵ It is important to point out that, while treating terrorism as a disease by analyzing and curing its causes; the analogy of war and crime can be applied too. A combination of these three perspectives is often needed. In cases when terrorists threaten or commit VA of terrorism, it does not mean that they should be sent to the hospital for treatment. In such situations governments may decide to use military strikes against terrorists (war on terrorism) or may decide to arrest and put them in jail (terrorism as crime).

A major component of treating this phenomenon as a disease is the implementation of several reforms. “Reform packages may become part of the government response in an effort to reduce the appeal of the terrorist groups within the population. If ethnic or religious discrimination is present, laws forbidding discrimination may be passed. If poverty is perceived to be fuelling support for the terrorists, then government programmes to reduce poverty in a region or group may be instituted (at least if the funds are available).”¹⁰⁶ If the war analogy is important due to the rising number of the terrorist organizations in the ME or if the analogy of crime is relevant because of the persistent VA of terrorism that are occurring in many countries, then, considering the fact that terrorism is a growing phenomenon, the analogy of treating it as a disease seems as the most needed approach (for now).

102 Peter J. Katzenstein, *Same War-Different Views: Germany, Japan, and Counterterrorism*, (The International Organization Foundation, 2003), 744.

103 *Ibid.*, 735.

104 *Ibid.*, 744.

105 *Ibid.*, 743.

106 Alan Collins, *Contemporary Security Studies*, (Oxford University Press, 2013), 284.

This approach seems to fit not only the Arab world but also Western countries. The reason is that there are cases when individuals who were born and raised in democratic countries, and who then joined the terrorist armed groups in the ME or committed VA of terrorism in their country were the result of the radicalizing campaigns that terrorists offer via the Internet.

3.5 When Terrorism Wins

Although it is considered a weapon of the weak, in some cases terrorism can win. The concerns that governments in some cases can abuse the human rights and freedoms in the name of national security are real in most democratic countries. As has been mentioned, considering terrorism as a problem that can be solved by military means gives governments greater powers and it legitimizes them to use preemptive strikes against terrorists. In spite of the fact that such a viewpoint is essential when it comes to dealing with terrorist organizations who have universal goals, such as Al Qaeda or ISIS, this analogy leaves room for the imagination. For example, we have some religious extremist groups who believe or claim to believe that our international order is failed because it was not established based on Islamic principles and they want to prove it by committing VA of terrorism against the many countries. But also we have countries that strongly support our international order and are willing to compromise some rights and freedoms that are considered as the pillars of democracy, in order to fight those terrorist groups that refuse to comply with our order. This is how the analogy of war leads to a situation where one must choose between bad alternatives. If the human rights and freedoms are the basic principles that governments must respect in order to be considered democratic, and these basic principles are violated for the sake of common security, then terrorism has reached its goal at some degree.

As a final point, terrorism wins when the reason of fighting against this phenomenon becomes infiltrated by hate. For instance, in recent times we have had the chance to hear statements given by politically influential people, where it can be said that hatred against terrorists was unjustly turned into hatred of a particular nation or community. It does not matter if these statements were really meant or were given only to gain political support. Knowing the fact that the main goals of terrorist organizations are to promote hatred and fear these statements have contributed in favour of terrorism as well. If these politicians allow themselves to make such reckless mistakes, then who guarantees that they are not going to do the same mistakes when they are in charge for serious matters. For this simple reason the justifications that some rights and freedoms must be compromised in order to deal with terrorism in the right way leaves room for imagination. It becomes hard to resist conclusions that terrorism is being used to justify some actions that are against democratic values.

4 RE in Kosovo

While many countries are confronted with the dangers that come from terrorism and are at the same time struggling to choose the right measures in order to treat it in a proper way, Kosovo, as a young country with only ten years of experience, has not remained untouched by this phenomenon. If the people of Kosovo would have to boast about a single virtue it would undoubtedly be religious tolerance. However, as a result of war's long-term effects and as a consequence of the poor political leadership after the war, the virtues and values of the Kosovar society were hit in every possible respect. Under those circumstances, RE also found its course because it cannot be fought in an effective way, while corruption and organized crime have taken place in every level of society.

4.1 Radicalization of Kosovars

In spite of the fact that more than 90% of the Kosovar population are Muslim, RE and intolerance were never rooted in the society because Kosovo practices one of the most moderate and tolerant Islamic schools called "Hanafi". However, after the armed conflict with Serbia in 1998-99, the early signs of RE began to emerge in Kosovo's society. This influence on non-tolerance came as a result of several organizations from the ME that were placed in Kosovo with humanitarian status, some imams who were educated in ME, and as a result of radical campaigns that were conducted in different ways.

It came as no surprise when it was reported and then confirmed by the authorities that 316 radicalized citizens had left Kosovo to join terrorist armed groups such as Al-Nusra and ISIS. If we compare the number of Kosovo foreign fighters who joined armed conflicts in Iraq and Syria with other countries that are dealing with the same problem, this number does not seem too concerning. However, considering the fact Kosovo has only 1.8 million inhabitants this number is shocking. Therefore, some scholars claim that in the continent of Europe, Kosovo has given the largest number of foreign fighters who joined terrorist armed groups in ME.

4.1.1 Kosovo's Counter-terrorism Measures

Along with the large number of radicals in Kosovo who had decided to join terrorist armed groups in the ME, it was even worse when it came to the conclusion that some of them had been able to be important figures in terrorist organizations such as ISIS and Al-Nusra. “Two Kosovans carried out suicide attacks in Iraq and a few others climbed to the top of ISIS hierarchy, one of which gained notoriety through a gruesome act of decapitation broadcast globally. Other Kosovans have carried out attacks on Western Europe and in the U.S.A.”¹⁰⁷ As a result the international media reported on these events and there was a considerable reaction from the international partners in Kosovo. After the VE came to the fore the Kosovo authorities have done a significant job by addressing this issue with police methods (treating terrorism as a crime).

In 2015 the Kosovo Assembly adopted a law that incriminates the participation of Kosovo citizens in foreign wars. Based on this law the Kosovo authorities could arrest and detain those individuals who joined terrorist armed groups in the ME then decided to return to Kosovo. “Kosovo has stepped up its activities to counter VE with more than 100 arrests and investigations launched against approximately 78 persons suspected of being involved in recruitment activities for the ISIS and Al Nusra.”¹⁰⁸ Also, in the same year, the Kosovo government has drafted a “Strategy on the Prevention of VE and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020” aiming to address the push and pull factors that lead Kosovo citizens to VE and also to define the roles and responsibilities for the actors both inside and outside the government.

As a result of the counter terrorism efforts by the security, since 2015, the number of Kosovo citizens who joined terrorist armed groups in the ME has sharply decreased. “Due to counter-terrorism activities by Kosovo police as well as the justice system, the number of Kosovans that leave Kosovo to join ISIS and other extremist groups has decreased substantially since 2015.”¹⁰⁹ Although this outcome may be considered as a success of treating terrorism as a crime; this does not necessarily indicate that RE in the Republic of Kosovo is being prevented. Routes that led Kosovo's people toward armed conflicts in the ME region

107 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 4.

108 Ibid., 4.

109 Ibid., 5.

were built over the last two decades. First, one part of Kosovar society was exposed to RE in open environments such as the largest mosque in Prishtina, where imam Shefqet Krasniqi used to cry and give convincing radical speeches. Then, the other part of society was radicalized in the closed environments such as the recruitment camp for jihadists, located in a rural zone near Gjilan city.

4.1.2 Is Kosovo Using the Right Measures?

The police methods of arresting and detaining those who were responsible for spreading RE in Kosovo that lead to radicalization of many people and also those who were part of terrorist armed groups in the ME and then returned to Kosovo can be seen as responsive actions in order to disable this negative impact on the society. However, arresting and detaining terrorist such individuals does not mean that their desires for jihad will be extinguished. That is a pessimistic scenario but it is possible that such individuals manage to radicalize the Kosovar society in a large-scale by turning it into a deeply intolerant society, from this arrest and imprisonment of suspected terrorists can be perceived as anti-Islamic activity which may lead to a violent resistance or even crisis. There is a growing possibility of terrorist attacks in Kosovo by radicalized people for mainly two reasons: (1) arresting and detaining extremist imams may be perceived as anti-Islamic movements, and (2) radicalized people may be motivated to commit VA of terrorism based on ISIS calls to all “Muslim brothers” to carry out attacks on their homeland.

This chapter will concentrate on push and pull factors that radicalized this society known for its religious tolerance. It is important to analyze where the RE came from and how it was served to the people of Kosovo which lead many radicalized individuals to join terrorist armed groups in the ME. Also it is important to analyze whether there have been early signs of radicalization in society and whether this negative influence could be prevented before it became late. The Kosovo authorities started addressing this issue under the pressure of international community only after the foreign media was describing Kosovo as a jihadist recruitment hub. Although late, the arrest and detention of individuals who were involved in terrorism-related activities were indispensable. However, dealing with terrorism often requires more than treating it with police methods. Therefore, Kosovo needs to do more in order to address this issue that is threatening the world.

4.2 The Role of Religion in Kosovo

With the spread of the OE in the Balkans during the XIII century Islamic religion was introduced in the region. It is said that during the Islamization of Balkans, a considerable number of Christian believers migrated to European countries, in order to survive from conversion, as it was obligatory. It is also believed that the Albanian people were willingly converted to Islamic faith because by being Muslim they integrated into the Ottoman and enjoyed the privileges offered by the empire. Both claims could be right. In this paper the discussion of Balkan Islamization has no other intention than giving a short description of where Islam in the Balkan came from. Perhaps an explanation where everyone could agree is that the OE ruled in Balkans for about five centuries and people had plenty of time to change their minds.

Based on the Kosovar population census that was carried out in the year of 2014 by the Kosovo Agency of Statistics (KAS), “over 90% of the population of Kosovo belong to the Islamic confession.”¹¹⁰ However, the religion practiced by older generations was different from the religion that was brought after the war with Serbia 1998-99. For instance, following the political decision of Slobodan Milosevic (then President of Serbia) to revoke Kosovo’s autonomy granted in 1974, people of Kosovo did not protest because of religious discrimination but because of ethnic discrimination. During the passive and armed resistance in 90s Kosovo’s leadership was oriented towards Western World and not towards the ME. This demonstrates that for people of Kosovo the nation was more important than the religion and based on this principle were built the values of religious tolerance. Within the Kosovo Albanian population religion was never considered as an instrument of political affairs but as an individual path to create one’s place after death.

One of the most important factors that contributed to religious tolerance in Kosovo, was practicing one of the four moderate and tolerant schools of Islam, Hanafi. This school allowed Kosovar Albanians to worship God and at the same time to live in harmony with believers of other sects and other cultures. According to Kosovar tradition, practice of Islam was considered as a privilege where one can do jihad by heart and not by imposition. The strategy which obligates all Muslims to do jihad in order to be real believers was never mentioned. After the war though, there was a new interpretation of the Islamic faith which was in contradiction with the values of the Kosovar society.

110 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 6.

4.2.1 Juridical Schools of Islam

Apart from the tolerant judicial school of Islam being practiced in Kosovo, scholars explain that there are three other strict and conservative judicial schools of Islam. “The oldest is the Hanafiyya school, followed by the Malikiyya school, Shafiyya and the latest, Hanbaliyya school.”¹¹¹ In comparison to Hanafi school, especially the latest school called Hanbalia, can be labeled as an extremist school because it considers the jihad as an obligatory strategy under any circumstances. From their point of view the other tolerant judicial schools of Islam such as Hanafi are considered as deviations from Islam because they have left behind the jihad strategy. “According to Lauziere, this interpretation considers all other Islamic traditions as deviation from true Islam and tends to influence both theological concepts as well as the social etiquette.”¹¹² This narrow-minded interpretation of Islam came to Kosovo as a result of some imams who were educated in the ME and some humanitarian organization from ME and it became known as Salafism. “The term Salafism in Kosovo is used interchangeably to describe the Hanbaliyya school and Wahabbism.”¹¹³

With the interpretation of this school in Kosovo signs of RE could be found everywhere in the Kosovar society. Muslim believers were considered to be the ones who practiced this intolerant school in a strict way and the rest were labeled as non-believers. “After the war, there has been an invasion of atypical interpretation of Islam for Kosovo, in which religion was paired with culture and preaching on how should people live, dress and dine, one participant explained.”¹¹⁴ To be a real Muslim it was not enough to practice religion by praying and living a moral life but it was also necessary to express, look and behave like an Arab. The traditional believers were being accused for the deviation of Islam because they were not praying in accordance with their expectation and they had neglected jihad.

The result of this was that the Muslim community in Kosovo was divided into two classes: (1) Traditional believers attended those mosques where religion was interpreted in a traditional way (Hanafi school), and (2) the others followed those mosques where religion was interpreted in a Salafist way (Hanbalia school). Misinterpretation of religion,

111 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 13.

112 Ibid., 13.

113 Ibid., 13.

114 Ibid., 13.

non-tolerance and hate speech became a day-to-day norm of the second class, which deeply affected the rise of RE in society. For example, some influential radical imams went so far, as to accuse the most eminent national figures of Kosovo. Skanderbeg was accused of being against the Albanian people because he fought against the Muslims (then OE). Also, they claimed that Mother Theresa belongs in hell because she was not Muslim. As can be seen the values of religious tolerance and everything that Kosovar people were proud of became a target of RE. In some cases there were occasions where traditional believers opposed the lectures of radical imams and quit attending the mosques where there was such interpretation.

4.2.2 The Role of Religion After the War in Kosovo

To find out that Kosovo society became more religious after the armed conflict with Serbia in 1998-99 no surveys are needed at all. It is enough to consider the fact that, right after the war, there were about 200 existing mosques¹¹⁵. Today there are more than 800 mosques in the territory of Kosovo. This shows that during the postwar period the number of mosques tripled and the demands for the construction of new mosques still persist. It is important to point out that these mosques are not just buildings that were constructed after the war. Especially on Fridays they are filled with a large number of people and often they are faced with situations like praying in the yard of the mosque or even in the street because there is no room inside. “Surveys conducted between 2012-2015 show that Kosovan society is becoming more religious, departing from the pre-war situation.”¹¹⁶ However, there is no need for concerns like the practice of religion by a large number of people is a threat to the national security of Kosovo. Such conclusion would definitely be wrong. For Kosovo institutions it is more important to make it clear that it is permissible to practice any religion in Kosovo, as long as they do not violate the human rights and freedoms that are written in the constitution.

An obstacle that blocks the prevention of RE in Kosovo is the fact that often local people choose their own imams or imams are directly assigned by those who built the mosque, whether an organization or a private sponsor. “In many cases, imams are selected by the local people or private sponsors of mosques and the Islamic Community of Kosovo (ICK) has

115 Frud Bezhan, *A Growing Split Between Islamic, Secular Identities In Kosovo*, (RadioFreeEurope/RadioLiberty 2016), <<https://www.rferl.org/a/kosovo-split-islamic-identity-secular-traditions/27906304.html>> accessed 10 May 2018.

116 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 7.

no influence in appointing imams.”¹¹⁷ This indicates that when an organization from the ME sponsors the construction of a mosque in the territory of Kosovo they have the right to pick the imam of that mosque and if the sponsoring organization supports jihad (which they normally do) they assign an imam who meets their expectations. This ungoverned situation has played a crucial role in radicalization of the community. Mosque sponsors can be labeled as a pulling factor that spread the RE in Kosovo; however they can not be labeled as the only cause in this process. The most blameworthy factor here is the Kosovo authorities because while the society was being radicalized left and right, it did not come into their consideration until it became too late. For example, some religious leaders from different municipalities of Kosovo argue that they tried to denounce individuals responsible for spreading RE but their denunciations were not taken into consideration by the authorities.

*“We have made several requests to police and municipal authorities to check some mosques where we believed extremist ideologies were being taught, but our appeals were not taken seriously. For example, in one case, the imam whom we denounced and no action was taken by the authorities, was arrested some years later for his involvement in recruitment for the war in Syria.”*¹¹⁸

Kosovo authorities were not concerned even when imams with radical beliefs were spreading their ideologies in public and in front of a large audience of young people who happened to be in a post-war country with the highest unemployment rate in the region. It is important to realize that only after the alarming number of radicalized Kosovars was confirmed that joined terrorist armed groups in the ME, only after the international media was describing Kosovo as a nest of jihadist recruitment under the pressure of the international community, did Kosovo authorities decide to arrest Shefqet Krasniqi (imam of the biggest mosque in Prishtina).

*“The Imam of the largest mosque in Prishtinë/Prishtina, the Mehmet Fatih Mosque, Shefqet Krasniqi, just a couple hundred meters from the KIC offices, has been charged recently, among other, for inciting people to join the conflict in Syria and inciting terrorist actions. According to Kosovo Special Prosecutor, during his service in the mosque and in social media, Krasniqi has actively influenced people to join the conflict zone in Syria and Iraq and to commit terrorist acts.”*¹¹⁹

117 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 5.

118 Ibid., 14.

119 Ibid., 5.

Law enforcement agencies may reasonably argue that there was a lack of legal basis for the prosecutions of Kosovo citizens who joined terrorist armed groups in the ME then returned to Kosovo because such a law did not exist in the criminal code of the Republic of Kosovo. As a result, in the year of 2015, “Kosovo Assembly also adopted the Law on the Prohibition on Joining Foreign Conflicts, under which members of ISIS and other extremist organizations returning to Kosovo are being prosecuted.”¹²⁰ However, law enforcement agencies can not reasonably argue that they did not have legal framework and evidence to prevent RE that was being spread in Kosovo.

4.2.3 Counter Terrorism Legal Framework

Excluding the law which permitted the prosecution of individuals who joined terrorist armed groups in the ME such as Al Nusra and ISIS, which was adopted by the Kosovo Assembly on 12 March 2015 Kosovo has had a comprehensive legal framework to counteract and prevent the spread of RE. Even the U.S Department of State has stated that “Kosovo has a comprehensive legal framework that covers all criminal aspects related to terrorism. The Criminal Code of Kosovo preserves the UN model on counterterrorism criminal legislation and criminalizes all forms of terrorism, including commission, assistance, facilitation, recruitment, training, and incitement to commit terrorism. It also criminalizes concealment or failure to report terrorists or terrorist groups, organization and participation in terrorist groups, and preparation of terrorist offenses against the constitutional order and the security of the state of Kosovo.”¹²¹ In the first place, it was easy for the security forces to identify and track the individuals or groups affected by radicalism in Kosovo because they looked, prayed and believed differently. By tracking radicalized citizens they could have easily find the location of recruiting places. Furthermore, those radical groups did not gain the support of the majority in Kosovo and often they were criticized for being in contradiction with the Kosovar values. The law enforcement agencies had all the necessary tools to prevent RE in Kosovo, instead they decided not to use them. For example, in the Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo it is written as follows:

120 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 11.

121 *Bureau of Counterterrorism and Countering Violent Extremism, Country Reports on Terrorism 2015*, (U.S Department of State 2015), <<https://www.state.gov/j/ct/rls/crt/2015/257516.htm>> accessed 11 May 2018.

Article 8 [Secular State]

*“The Republic of Kosovo is a secular state and is neutral in matters of religious beliefs.”*¹²²

Article 21 [General Principles] Paragraph 3

*“Everyone must respect the human rights and fundamental freedoms of others.”*¹²³

Article 24 [Equality Before the Law] Paragraph 2

*“No one shall be discriminated against on grounds of race, color, gender, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, relation to any community, property, economic and social condition, sexual orientation, birth, disability or other personal status.”*¹²⁴

Article 38 [Freedom of Belief, Conscience and Religion] Paragraph 4

*“Freedom of manifesting religion, beliefs and conscience may be limited by law if it is necessary to protect public safety and order or the health or rights of other persons.”*¹²⁵

Article 40 [Freedom of Expression] Paragraph 2

*“The freedom of expression can be limited by law in cases when it is necessary to prevent encouragement or provocation of violence and hostility on grounds of race, nationality, ethnicity or religion.”*¹²⁶

Article 42 [Freedom of Media] Paragraph 2

*“Censorship is forbidden. No one shall prevent the dissemination of information or ideas through media, except if it is necessary to prevent encouragement or provocation of violence and hostility on grounds of race, nationality, ethnicity or religion.”*¹²⁷

Article 58 [Responsibilities of the State] Paragraph 3

*“The Republic of Kosovo shall take all necessary measures to protect persons who may be subject to threats or acts of discrimination, hostility or violence as a result of their national, ethnic, cultural, linguistic or religious identity.”*¹²⁸

122 The Constitution of the Republic of Kosovo, (2008), 2.

123 Ibid., 6.

124 Ibid., 7.

125 Ibid., 11.

126 Ibid., 12.

127 Ibid., 12.

128 Ibid., 16.

If the laws of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kosovo were properly executed at an early stage of the radicalization of Kosovo society, all the RE activities that later lead to terrorism could have been prevented. To demonstrate, in Chapter XIV, there are 13 articles in total that could be used to deal with activities related to terrorism. However, due to the page limitation of this paper not all articles of the Criminal Code that are related to terrorism will be described. The articles covering terrorist activities in Kosovo are: Terrorism definition, Commission of the offense, Assistance in the commission, Facilitation of the commission, Recruitment, Training, Incitement to commit a terrorist offense, Concealment or failure to report terrorists, Organization or participation in a terrorist group and Preparation of terrorist offenses. Fortunately, Kosovo has yet to experience attacks like the VA of terrorism that are occurring in European countries. However, there are concerns about terrorism in Kosovo. RE has grown rapidly and that is why a large number of Kosovars have decided to join armed terrorist groups in the ME. It is important to point out some of the articles of the Criminal Code that could be applied to prevent the spread of RE in Kosovo. One of the most useful articles that could be used against the spread of RE in Kosovo is:

Article 147 [Inciting national, racial, religious or ethnic hatred, discord or intolerance]

“1. Whoever publicly incites or publicly spreads hatred, discord or intolerance between national, racial, religious, ethnic or other such groups living in the Republic of Kosovo in a manner which is likely to disturb public order shall be punished by a fine or by imprisonment of up to five (5) years.

2. Whoever commits the offense provided for in paragraph 1 of this Article in a systematic manner or by taking advantage of his or her position or authority or causes disorder, violence, or other grave consequences by the commission of such offense shall be punished by imprisonment from one (1) to eight (8) years.

3. Whoever commits the offense provided for in paragraph 1 of this Article by means of coercion, jeopardizing safety, exposing national, racial, ethnic or religious symbols to derision, damaging the belongings of another person, or desecrating monuments or graves shall be punished by imprisonment of one (1) to eight (8) years.

4. Whoever commits the offense provided for in paragraph 3 of this Article in a systematic manner or by taking advantage of his or her position or authority or causes disorder, violence or other grave consequences by the commission of such offense shall be punished by imprisonment of two (2) to ten (10) years.¹²⁹

129 Criminal Code of the Republic of Kosovo, (2013), 69-70.

Article 138 [Facilitation of the commission of terrorism] Paragraph 1

“Whoever by any means directly or indirectly provides, solicits, collects or conceals funds or material resources with the intent, knowledge or reasonable grounds for belief that they will be used in whole or in part, for or by a terrorist group or for the commission of a terrorist act shall be punished by imprisonment of five (5) to fifteen (15) years.”¹³⁰

Article 139 [Recruitment for terrorism]

“Whoever solicits another person to commit or participate in the commission of a terrorist offense, to participate in the activities of a terrorist group or to provide funds or material resources shall be punished by imprisonment of five (5) to fifteen (15) years.”¹³¹

Article 141 [Incitement to commit a terrorist offense]

“Whoever distributes, or otherwise makes available, a message to the public, with the intent to incite the commission of a terrorist offense, where such conduct, whether or not directly advocating terrorist offenses, causes a danger that one or more such offenses may be committed, shall be punished by imprisonment of one (1) to five (5) years.”¹³²

Kosovo authorities clearly had at their disposal all the necessary tools to prevent RE as it was spreading to the society although they did not take measures until it was reported that a large number of citizens had joined terrorist armed groups such as ISIS and Al-Nusra. Instead of focusing on radical imams, Kosovo institutions decided to prohibit wearing head scarf (hijab) for students in public schools, which raised concerns among the public opinion. “In 2010, the Ministry of education has issued an administrative instruction banning wearing of head-scarf by students in public schools.”¹³³ Although this decision made by Ministry of Education may be seen as a reaction against the fact that Kosovo was becoming more religious, it was not an appropriate decision because it especially angered radicalized people. As a result, a group of fanatic supporters of wearing head scarfs took to the streets to protest against this decision by chanting Arab expressions in the capital. The vast majority of Kosovars were shocked, not because they had come to protest against the removal of the head scarf but because of which group of people had gone out and how they were protesting. They were dressed as Arabs, shouting in Arabic language and you could easily tell that they have been radicalized. Yet, even this event did not concern the Kosovo authorities.

130 Criminal Code of the Republic of Kosovo, (2013), 66.

131 Ibid., 66.

132 Ibid., 67.

133 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 14.

4.3 Push Factors

Like in many parts of the world there are several factors pushing individuals towards RE and there is no universal cause that everybody could agree upon. **Push factors**¹³⁴ that affect one country, may be non-existent or may not affect the other country in the same way. While in developed countries push factors can be considered the desires of individuals to become a part of a “big adventure” or to do something “meaningful,” in Kosovo this is a matter that requires the consideration of several factors that affected the society in a long run. “In the case of Kosovo, the main driving factors are the essential and structural factors such as the economic and social challenges/ weaknesses and inadequate institutional capacity and their integrity. These are long-term weakness in Kosovo society that causes a wide range of issues, not being limited to violent extremism only.”¹³⁵

4.3.1 Socio-economic Challenges

Although the Kosovo people can brag about positive events such as the NATO intervention during the ethnic cleansing in Kosovo, carried out by Milosevic’s regime in 1999, or the declaration of independence from Serbia in 2008 and the recognition from many states that play an important role in IR Kosovo has still a long way to remove itself from the map of fragile states. It has entered the second decade as an independent state and is still listed as one of the countries with the highest unemployment rate in Europe. The United Nations Development Program in Kosovo (UNDP) demonstrates that unemployment rate in general stands at 32.9%, and the unemployment rate of youth (aged 15 to 24 years) stands at 57.7%.¹³⁶ This shows that the people of Kosovo have a strong reason to be unhappy. For a small country like Kosovo the number of employees working in the government administration is large and most of them are hired due to family or political party ties. “In terms of territorial compactness and population, Kosovo has a large number of public administration institutions and employees thereof.”¹³⁷ This high number of government officials is not because the political leadership

134 In this paper, the push factor means, the factor that drives individuals to be victims of RE that leads to terrorism.

135 Government of Kosovo, *Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020*, (2015), 13.

136 *Introduction About Kosovo*, (United Nations Development Programme UNDP), <<http://www.ks.undp.org/content/kosovo/en/home/countryinfo.html>> accessed 12 May 2018.

137 GAP Institute, *Reforming Public Administration in Kosovo - A proposal to Decrease the Number of Employees in the Public Administration*, (2015), 2.

was thinking to reduce the unemployment in Kosovo but because the political leadership was seeking to create loyal circles which they can count on during the election time. The Kosovar society is a witness how corruption, nepotism and organized crime became a day-to-day norm of the post-war era, while a group of political leaders was getting wealthy. Consequently, all this atmosphere increased the disappointment and distrust of the society towards the state institutions; therefore a large number of young people have considered leaving.

An important finding of researchers studying RE in Kosovo is that the majority of radicalized people have no religious background or come from non-religious families. Due to lack of knowledge about religion, they easily accept what is being said without comparing or criticizing it. “Recruiters provide young men discriminate or false information about religion, and due to the lack of previous religious education, they become a prey to radicalization. In contrast, the elderly and those that already have traditional religious education are less prone to indoctrination.”¹³⁸

Figure 4.1: Participant responses on the push factors of VE¹³⁹

138 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 14.

139 Ibid., 17.

As a result of a bad leadership, the mentality of fraud and doing public services in exchange of bribery was installed in every state institution. In the health care institutions benefiting from patients became more important than treating and curing them. Patients had to give bribes in order to get treatments in the hospitals and those who could not afford it had to wait longer, did not get the right treatment or did not get treatment at all. Similarly within the judicial system, instead of finding the truth and serving justice, profit mattered more than anything. With the educational system, financial benefits from students became more important than teaching and providing them with quality education. This is how they produced useless graduates. For example, many students were allowed to register in universities, get a marks or even graduate, by giving bribes and other favours. Why doctors, judges and professors should not do it, when the “saviours of the nation” were doing it? Under those circumstances, corruption and organized crime became a day-to-day norm in society and all the values were distorted. While the role of religion was continuously growing, finding a job was not easy and a large number of young people found themselves in a situation without any aspiration. Religion seemed to be an alternative in order to keep oneself busy because man was created to do something. In conclusion, this is how a group of young people who had no knowledge about religion ended up in the hands of some religious extremists: there at least it was not required to be a member of a certain political party in order to be accepted.

4.4 Pull Factors

An element that is broadly considered to be a **pull factor**¹⁴⁰ which leads people to RE is globalization. Not everybody will agree with such a generalization. It is true that the inventiveness of globalization has made it easier for terrorists to recruit new members and spread their ideology through internet channels. But globalization can also be useful to build resilience against terrorism or even turn a conservative community into a more tolerant one. So when the question arises, “How does globalization affect terrorism?” the answer depends on the cause. On one hand, globalization can be dangerous when used by terrorist organizations to achieve their goals. But conversely it can be used to fight against terrorism and prevent its VA. After all, the point where everyone could agree is that terrorist organizations have managed to use the Internet to a great extent. Many researchers claim that social media has become a useful tool for terrorist to do radicalization campaigns and recruit

140 In this paper, the pull factor means, the factor that attract individuals to be victims of RE that leads to terrorism.

new members. It has been noted that in Kosovo extremist imams have used the internet channels and other media to spread their beliefs and thoughts, playing a key role in the spread of RE. “An imam from Kosovo, who has recently been charged with inciting religious and other hatred, broadcasted regularly via YouTube and paid TV time.”¹⁴¹

Another major factor are individuals who were educated in the ME and then returned to work as imams in Kosovo. “Informal areas where these extremist imams deliver their religious lectures, including sports halls, YouTube, paid TV shows, have been noted in all focus groups.”¹⁴² As a result of these imams educated in the ME and the religious literature containing radical texts that was published in the Albanian language; traditional believers of Islam started being targeted as a deviation from the real Islam. “For over a decade extremist literature was published by various organizations and they circulated uncontrolled.”¹⁴³ A recent initiative taken by the Ministry of Justice (MJ) to check the prison libraries had found that “most literature in the prison libraries has radical and extremist content.”¹⁴⁴ Among the many pull factors, one can say that ME educated imams and the literature with radical religious content played the main role in the interpretation of one of the most strict Islamic schools in Kosovo which is known as Salafism.

Figure 4.2: Participant responses on pull factors of VE¹⁴⁵

141 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 18.

142 Ibid., 18.

143 Ibid., 18.

144 Ibid., 18.

145 Ibid., 19.

The role of religion was growing in the post-war Kosovo and the radical religious lecturers were speaking louder. It is not known whether there was a coordination between these extremist imams educated in the ME or not. However, it could be said that everything that was considered to be a value in Kosovo was being targeted by this group. Add to this that Arab style of living was becoming more present, practicing religion in a moderate way was being considered as a deviation, religious tolerance was being considered a weakness and national figures were being targeted. Finally, the radical imams started considering themselves as an important factor for the society because they have brought this influence in Kosovo. Therefore, they could give themselves the right to decide who is going to heaven and who to hell.

4.5 Attracted population segments to RE

Due to the large Muslim community, terrorist organizations with jihadist ideology have viewed the Balkans as an attractive region to spread their ideologies and recruit new members. “Kosovo and the countries in the region are seen as appropriate places to recruit fighters for extremist / terrorist groups such as ISIS and similar.”¹⁴⁶ The strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020 drafted by the Government of Kosovo, emphasizes the need for the creation of a team to gather information about the segments of the population that are vulnerable to radicalism in Kosovo. “Including the regions / locations most affected, target age, ethnical demographics and other, recruiters and support organizations, narratives of recruitment and the methods used by them.”¹⁴⁷ Such methods can harm people who match the profile but have nothing to do with terrorism and rarely bring satisfying results. Unfortunately, there is no such profile that describes vulnerable people to RE, just like there is no profile that uncovers terrorists before they have committed a terrorist attack. To illustrate, in Germany, “The statistical profile of potential suspects was comprised of twenty to thirty-five, from the ME, enrolled in engineering schools and without previous criminal convictions. The operation turned out to be a flop; after several months no single “sleeper” terrorist had been identified. Published reports about arrest of seven suspected members of a new cell in Hamburg did not fit the statistical profile. One member was fifty-one years old; another was a German citizen; and some had not been university students.”¹⁴⁸

146 Government of Kosovo, *Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020*, (2015), 11.

147 Ibid., 19.

148 Peter J. Katzenstein, *Same War-Different Views: Germany, Japan, and Counterterrorism*, (The International Organization Foundation, 2003), 751.

One may assume that people get easily radicalized due to lack of education just to be surprised that a considerable number of Kosovo citizens who decided to join armed terrorist groups in the ME had higher levels of education. In addition, the concerns that rural areas are more prone to RE are not sustainable. According to a survey conducted by Kosovo Center for Security Studies, the commitment of rural and urban areas to religion does not seem so dissimilar. “The Kosovo Security Barometer shows that 10% would commit to a religious rather than a national cause, while approximately 46% would commit to both national and religious causes.”¹⁴⁹ Some of the jihadist recruiters have avoided urban areas and decided to stay in areas with a small number of residents like Elez Han because in such isolated places they could operate without being detected. Nevertheless, this does not mean that these sites were visited by rural residents only. For these reasons, it is difficult to create a certain profile that would help to identify which population segments are more attracted to jihadist ideology.

Regarding the gender concern, the distinction between men and women traveling to ME to join armed terrorist groups is sharp. “In the case of Kosovo out of a total of 316 citizens who have joined ISIS, 44 are women, 7 of which have returned.”¹⁵⁰ The reason behind this distinction is that recruiters first sought to recruit men so they could be used in armed conflicts in the ME region. In addition, “at the initial stages, extremist organizations did not recruit women — this began only when “state building” was introduced by ISIS, predominantly, in the conquered territory.”¹⁵¹ A considerable number of women that ended up in the ME, they went there because their man had decided to join armed terrorist groups such as ISIS and Al-Nusra. The numbers shown above do not indicate that women in Kosovo are more resistant to RE; they were just less exposed to this global phenomenon. Most of extremists educated in the ME were males and when they returned to work as imams in Kosovo, they also gave lectures to male listeners because they do not allow both genders in the same room. But if there were more extremist females working as imams in Kosovo, of course that the number of radicalized women would be higher.

149 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 8.

150 Ibid., 12.

151 Ibid., 12.

5 Research Methodology

This chapter describes in chronological order the entire academic process that was used to complete this research paper. First, it explains the importance of the chosen topic and the strategy that the author chose to complete the research. Second it describes in a concise and precise way the methodological approach. Third the sub-chapter shows how the author has collected and selected the relevant data for the research. Fourth, it briefly describes the type and nature of the used data, whether it can be considered as reliable data for the academic world or not. And finally, considering the fact that no paper can answer all the questions, this chapter ends by briefly stating some of the limitations of this study. The purpose of this chapter is to describe how the author completed this study in order to serve as guide to the reader. Moreover, during the preparation of the master thesis, the description of the research methodology is an academic criterion which is expected from student in order to successfully graduate.

5.1 Research Strategy

Having in mind that terrorism is a growing phenomenon which constantly poses threats to the national security of many countries, I chose terrorism as a topic for my master thesis in order to familiarize myself with a broader range of concepts. We often see on the news how individuals or groups commit VA of terrorism in the name of religion. We are also aware that armed terrorist groups are becoming actors in the discipline of RE, aiming to expand their influence as far as they can. Given these points, terrorism sparked my curiosity to learn more about this phenomenon. Therefore, I decided to concentrate on RE that leads to terrorism because currently this type of terrorism endangers the national security of Kosovo and the international security. I have had basic knowledge about the main terrorist organizations and the methods they use to generate fear. However, I found it essential to further deepen and explore the origins of RE. Why do terrorist organizations seek to overthrow our international order that was established with the Westphalia Treaty and based on what they seek such thing? Based on these reasons, I have considered that it is necessary to focus on ME history. In order to learn more about the origins of RE in the ME, I have studied the book of Henry Kissinger, titled “World Order”. And to understand the international relations of the Arab world, I have studied Louise Fawcett’s book titled “International Relations of the Middle East”.

During research on RE I have discovered how the standpoints of the extremist religious ideologues of the ME are similar with the RE that was brought to Kosovo after the war. In order to understand more about terrorism as a contemporary phenomenon, I studied Alan Collin's book, "Contemporary Security Studies." In this book it is explained that terrorism can be viewed from three different perspectives: as war, crime, and disease (Peter Sederberg's theory). Given the fact that Kosovo is affected by this phenomenon I decided to test this theory in the case of Kosovo and use it as a case study. In order to verify from which of these three viewpoints are the Kosovo institutions seeing terrorism, I have used the document published by the Government of Kosovo, titled "Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020". Also, I have referred to the Public Pulse analysis on "Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo", which has been very useful during the realization of this study.

5.1.1 Research Process

To begin with I gathered considerable materials that provided actual facts about the chosen topic. In order to get a general idea and identify what literature can be useful for my study I scanned through all the collected material, whether in book or digital form. After that I started reading and analyzing in detail all of the selected literature underlining each word, sentence or paragraph that seemed relevant or interesting for the research. This method was very useful for me because in this way there was no need to go back and read all of the literature from the beginning, instead referring only to the underlined rows. Any underlined phrase from the selected literature that I found it important to compare, criticize or elaborate I have done so by using critical thinking. All phrases of other authors used to complete this study have been fully detailed in a footnote for the sake of rules and transparency. It is important to point out that in order to complete Chapter IV, which treats RE in Kosovo as a case study, I have used the Public Pulse report that was composed of focus groups. This report was conducted by three focus groups, mainly concentrated in Prishtina, Gjilan and Hani i Elezit. "Participants were recruited based on their expertise and functions in various religious issues and bodies, central and local public institutions, educational institutions and civil society, as well as based on their involvement in both prevention and countering of radicalization and violent extremism."¹⁵²

152 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 26.

5.2 Data Collection

In order to find appropriate literature that could be used to construct this paper it was necessary to collect literature and documentation from local and foreign authors. And, in order to provide the appropriate answer to each of the research questions raised in this paper, it was essential to analyze and compare all the relevant material that has been gathered. To enlarge my understanding about the history of the ME (Chapter II), I have used books such as “World Order” and “International Relations of the Middle East.” Whereas in Chapter III, which focuses on terrorism as a worldwide phenomenon, I studied the book named “Contemporary Security Studies.” As for Chapter IV, focusing on Kosovo’s RE, I searched on the Internet for reports and research papers conducted by locals and I also used the Kosovo Constitution and the Criminal Code.

5.2.1 The Nature of Data

The nature of data used to conduct this research paper is mainly qualitative but to some extent, quantitative data was used as well. The data used to complete this study can be considered as structured data because most of it has been carefully written by scholars, researchers or government officials. This data contains factual information that covers terrorism as contemporary phenomenon and the RE in Kosovo as a specific case. The data used in this paper is not limited only to structured data completed by a single author or a group of researchers but there is reflective data, presented by the author’s personal experiences and thoughts.

5.2.2 Reliability and Validity

Considering the fact that the information used to conduct the research is well structured data by respected scholars in the academic world, I am confident that this paper represents the social reality in a suitable way. During the work process the historical records structured by other authors that have been interpreted or elaborated are also cited in the original structure and detailed with a footnote so that this paper might be transparent

and reliable for the reader. Having in mind that for master degree professors expect that students are able to do independent research rather than descriptive research, I was obliged to analyze, compare and elaborate on all the literature that was considered to be relevant with the topic of the study. It is important to note that all the comments, viewpoints, and conclusions (except for the cited phrases with a footnote) are my personal thoughts. The information used to complete the case study, describe in a proper way the social reality in Kosovo and can be considered as a reliable source that is relevant to the topic. In order to complete the critical chapter, I gathered reports and documentation that contain factual information, conducted by Kosovo institutions. I have also used research reports that were conducted by non-government organizations in order to analyze RE in Kosovo. Whenever this data was elaborated and interpreted it was also cited in the original way in order to make this paper as reliable as possible for the reader.

5.3 Research Limitations

For those who want to do research on RE that leads to terrorism there is sufficient material that can be found as printed text books in libraries or in digital format on the Internet. Because of the changing nature of terrorism as an old phenomenon scholars have described it in various ways. Therefore there are several theories and definitions about terrorism. They may differ and in some cases contradict one another. However, they are equally important because they represent different social realities. This research is limited because it has not been possible to include in this paper all the possible theories related to terrorism. In the book titled “Contemporary Security Studies” scholars argue that terrorism does not necessarily derive only from religion because there may be ethnic or ideological reasons that cause terrorism. This study, though, is focused in RE that leads to terrorism. It is important to consider that at the present time terrorism is a growing phenomenon and it has not been possible to analyze all the terrorist events. While writing this paper there were several terrorist attacks in the ME, Europe and US. Thus, trying to include all the terrorist incidents that are happening continuously would result in an unfinished work.

6 Summary of Theoretical Discussion

Since the theoretical discussion of this paper expands into three chapters such as (2) Islam in the ME, (3) Terrorism and (4) RE in Kosovo; for the sake of brevity, this chapter gives an overview of these three chapters. Considering the theoretical discussion done the aim of this chapter is to specifically examine each of the theoretical chapters and then to re-discuss in a short way the main finding of the research. This chapter will provide the reader with a brief summary in order to remind them the main findings before reaching the conclusions and recommendations.

6.1 Islam in the ME

In the second chapter we learned that the Prophet Muhammad received a divine vision from God so he began to convince other people that Islam was the right path and it needs to be the world's religion. The strategy to spread Islam throughout the world even today is called jihad. They managed to spread the religion, turning it into an empire. Since the prophet passed away in 632, though, the religious empire he had formed was divided to Sunni and Shia doctrines, and then finally collapsed. The next empire that took the mission of jihad was the OE created by the Turks in the 13th century. This empire grew rapidly and became a dominant force in the region. Ottomans also considered it important to spread the Islamic religion in all directions until world peace was achieved. Due to several uprisings and crisis within the empire, though, the OE was weakened and defeated by the Russian Empire. At the end of nineteenth century the OE was not considered by the GP as a force that posed military threats for them but its great territorial holdings in the Balkans and ME were viewed as causes that may result on the destabilization of the equilibrium of forces. Because of this the GP (England and France) stressed to organize plans and meetings in order to share the holdings of the OE without getting into conflict. The calls of the Arab World for self-government were not taken into consideration because at that time the GP considered that the Arab provinces in the ME, that had been ruled by the OE, needed to be tutored before becoming independent.

Unfortunately, the GP drafted plans for the partition of Arab lands based on national interests and not based on the liberal perspective which was suggested by President Wilson. For this reason, Arabs were not allowed to decide for their land as they wished and this failure to consider their willingness gave Arabs the impression that the Western World is not working for their good.

After the second World War (WWII), the mandating powers were exhausted by warfare so they could not manage to keep up the order in the ME region. At the same time, some of the monarchical governments were overthrown by their military leaders. The US and the SU, as the two superpowers of the world committed themselves to expanding their influence in the region for reasons like (1) finding large oil reserves in the ME when the countries with developed industries were dependent on it, and (2) the rivalry between the two superpowers to install their ideological order in the region during the CW. This rivalry between the two superpowers during the CW worsened the relations in the ME by deepening internal tensions in the region and also creating new ones. Scholars have noted that even when there was an initiative for political reforms in the Arab World they did not survive the pressure of the CW. Those initiatives were seen as movements supported by one or the other superpower and ultimately got crushed by non-democratic groups. This period allowed dictators to rule without the electorate's support. They made the political activities a very dreadful tool by suppressing any individual who raises the voice against the government.

Among the main factors that have paralysed the evolution of domestic politics in the ME is the great availability of oil resources in the region. Governments in industrialized countries offer goods and services to their citizens and, in the name of common good, they impose taxes. In countries with large oil reserves in the ME it is a different story because the state does not necessarily depend on the society. This is because governments in oil-producing countries can cover the state's expenses with the benefits of exporting oil to other countries. Due to the fact that the leaders (dictators) do not depend on the taxation of the citizens they don't consider it obligatory to give accounts to the people. Large oil reserves made it possible for dictators like Saddam Hussein to rule the country for a long period of time and using their absolute power to crush anyone who opposed his leadership. As a consequence, the political opposition was left in the hands of religious ideologues. Author Louise Fawcett rightly argues that, after all, dictators in Islamic countries could not shut down the mosques too.

6.2 Terrorism

In the third chapter we learned that terrorism is an old phenomenon and it does not necessarily derive from religion because the motives can be religious, ethnic or ideological. The reality is that religious terrorism is a growing phenomenon which has made many countries to consider it as the main threat to their national security. Therefore, this study is dedicated to the RE that leads to terrorism. Terrorist organizations claim that our world order is failure and seek to replace it with a religion-based order which dates from the seventh century. It becomes even more difficult when such organizations support their cause by committing VA of terrorism, killing and injuring many people. We also learned that measures that work to combat terrorism in one country may not be effective in another country. This paper, uses Peter Sederberg's theory, which argues that this phenomenon can be fought with military actions (as war), police methods (as crime), and by treating its causes and symptoms (as disease). It is therefore necessary for policy makers to identify in what way terrorism endangers their national security, in order to determine the appropriate measures to prevent it.

We learned about the challenges that countries and the IC face in defining terrorism. An individual or a group that is considered to be a terrorist in a certain community may not be viewed from the same perspective in other communities. Due to the shifting nature of terrorism there is no single definition because officials describe this phenomenon based on their experiences. The definition used in this study (Lutz and Lutz 2008: 9) includes six elements. The sixth element states that terrorism is a weapon of the weak. As an illustration, terrorist organizations such as ISIS and Al Qaeda are unable to overthrow our international order and install a religious-based one; therefore, they have turned to VA of terrorism. While attacks on public institutions are becoming infrequent due to enhanced security measures, terrorist attacks on public places where a large number of civilians can be hit are becoming frequent. Such places can be sports stadiums, squares, tourist sites, concerts, shopping malls and so on. There are several techniques that these groups or individuals use to achieve their objectives. However, at the present time, two of the most commonly used techniques are suicidal attacks with explosive devices and close quarter attacks. These techniques allow terrorists to reach unnoticed to public places and detonate their device or shoot in mass, aiming to kill and wound a large number of people.

In the past terrorist groups or organizations have posed threats to a certain country or community. Today, though, terrorist organizations have broadened their objectives by operating across borders and endangering many countries. They have managed to use to their own advantage the achievements of globalization. For example, terrorist organizations use the Internet as a tool to spread threats, give messages or even for recruiting purposes. Concurrently, other achievements such as the advancement of technology and transportation make it easier for terrorists to coordinate their actions without being detected by the authorities.

Finally, in spite of the fact that terrorism is considered to be weapon of the weak there are cases in which terrorism can win. As has been noted many times in this paper, terrorist organizations like ISIS and Al Qaeda claim that our international order is illegitimate and they aim to weaken it by committing VA of terrorism against many countries in order to generate fear and push them toward unreasonable actions. Therefore, especially the democratic countries that fight terrorism with analogy of war, must be careful when it comes to compromising the human rights and freedoms. Governments that decide to compromise these rights in the name of security and stability become less democratic and creating such norms in society definitely harms the concept of liberalism.

6.3 RE in Kosovo

In the fourth chapter it was noted that Kosovo as a young country has been affected by terrorism too. Although 90% of the Kosovar population adhere to the Muslim religion RE has not been a factor in the society. That is because in Kosovo was practiced one of the most moderate and tolerant schools of Islam called Hanafi. This moderate interpretation of Islam allowed Muslim believers to be able to practice their religion and at the same time live in peace with the communities adhering other religions. The practice of moderate Islam became a part of the tradition in Kosovo and in this way the values of the religion tolerance where built. After the war with Serbia 1998-99 the early signs of RE began to appear in the society. Due to several humanitarian organizations from the ME placed in Kosovo, imams educated in the ME and the religious literature containing radical texts that was published in the Albanian language; in Kosovo was introduced one of the most extreme schools of Islam called Hanibalia (Salafism).

The Salafism movement considers moderate schools like Hanafi as a deviation from true Islam because they have neglected the strategy of jihad. As such, even traditional believers started being labeled as deviation by this branch. With the interpretation of this radical school praying five times a day and living an honest life was not enough because the religion had to be fulfilled by embracing Arab culture and traditions.

On one hand, there were many traditional believers who opposed the interpretation of this school because hatred speech, intolerance, and distorted interpretation of religion began to be imposed as norms in the Muslim community. On the other hand, as a consequence of socio-economic problems, a large number of young people found themselves in a situation with no future. And thus decided to join these groups without having any background knowledge about religion. As a result of the radicalization of the society 316 Kosovo citizens traveled to ME to join terrorist armed groups such as ISIS and Al-Nusra. In spite of the fact that there were early signs of RE in society and there were also reportings to the police they were not taken into consideration by Kosovo institutions. The Kosovo authorities began to deal with this phenomenon only after the international media started describing Kosovo as a jihadist recruitment place.

The authorities have managed to address this problem quite well by arresting citizens that returned from terrorist armed conflicts in the ME and also arresting extremist imams responsible for the radicalization of society. Arrests, trials, and punishments of individuals involved in terrorist activities are included in the analogy of treating terrorism as crime (one of Sederberg's arguments). The problem is that imprisonment of such individuals does not solve the problem of RE in Kosovo because they can continue their radicalization activities even inside the prison or there may be cases where they get released if there is no sufficient evidence. Therefore, it is necessary to raise awareness and built resilience against RE that leads to terrorism (treating terrorism as a disease).

7 Research Analysis

Fortunately the great majority of Kosovo citizens love the values of the modern world and they are committed to becoming a part of the European Union. The influence of RE that was brought in Kosovo after the war, is not supported by the majority of population. Kosovo was once an example for religious tolerance values and could boast of how three of the world's largest religions could live in harmony in a small territory. Even though those values were attacked after the war RE did not win the majority of popular support because radicalism was considered as a foreign influence that did not match with the traditional values. The values of religious tolerance were built as a result of two factors: (1) the practice of one of the most tolerant schools of Islam (Hanafi) by older generations, enabling them to worship the God and live in peace with the communities of other religions. (2) Those values were further strengthened after the NATO intervention in Kosovo to stop the ethnic cleansing that was being carried out by the Milosevic's regime during 1998-99 and allow refugees to return to their homes. For such humanitarian intervention the people of Kosovo will always be thankful to the Western world.

While many countries are struggling to determine the right measures to deal with this growing phenomenon the rise of RE and the large number of Kosovars who joined the terrorist armed groups in the ME are the challenges that Kosovo must address in this period. The actions taken by security forces against individuals who were involved in terrorist activities were crucial in stopping the rise of RE in Kosovo. In 2015 the Kosovo Assembly adopted a law which prohibits the people of Kosovo to participate in foreign wars. With the adoption of this law the authorities were able to arrest and detain those citizens who were part of terrorist armed conflicts in the ME and then returned to Kosovo. "Kosovo has stepped up its activities to counter violent extremism with more than 100 arrests and investigations launched against approximately 78 persons suspected of being involved in recruitment activities for the ISIS and Al Nusra."¹⁵³ In the same year the Government of Kosovo has drafted a "Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020." The aim of this strategy is to assign the roles and responsibilities for actors inside and outside the government. At the present time the MJ has drafted a law for updating the Criminal Code of Kosovo

153 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 4.

but has not yet entered into force. Rule of law institutions want to improve the Criminal Code so they can have a wider scope when dealing with terrorism, organized crime, and corruption in Kosovo. They want to impose harsher sanctions against people who violate the law. Therefore, it can be said that the Kosovo authorities have achieved success in fighting terrorism with police methods (treating terrorism as crime).

A considerable number of radical imams have been arrested and found guilty of incited hatred and incitement to commit terrorist acts. Also a number of individuals who participated in the terrorist armed conflicts in the ME and then returned to Kosovo are already serving the prison sentences. All these methods of treating terrorism with the analogy of crime indicate that individuals involved in terrorism activities will be brought to justice and will be punished. This methodology is necessary to hold accountable individuals that have violated the law and at the same time to discourage others from getting involved in terrorism activities by showing them how they can end up. However, treating terrorism as a crime does not mean that it eliminates it altogether nor does it extinguish the desires of religious extremists for jihad. Therefore, having succeeded in the direction of treating terrorism as crime it is necessary for the state institutions to start drafting long-term strategies that would help in treating this phenomenon as a disease.

In spite the fact that this strategy has been criticized for being drafted in rush by the government due to international pressure to address the RE in Kosovo the “Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020” is a good start of treating terrorism as crime and disease for a short period of time. This strategy, though, drafted by the Government of Kosovo, mentions four times that it will be implemented “with the possibility of annual update.”¹⁵⁴ An important part of this strategy for the prevention of RE that leads to terrorism is that this document focuses on four strategic objectives as the following:

- Early identification - of the causes, factors and target groups.
- Prevention - of violent extremism and radicalization.
- Intervention - with the aim of preventing the risk from violent radicalization.
- De-radicalization and reintegration - of radicalized persons.¹⁵⁵

154 Government of Kosovo, *Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020*, (2015), 18-21-23-25.

155 Ibid., 18.

One of the main features of this strategy is that it attempts to achieve these strategic objectives for a period of five years by assigning the roles that actors inside and outside the government will play when dealing with terrorism. For example one of the specific measures in the function of de-radicalization and reintegration of radicalized individuals is “Provision of psychological and religious counselling for prisoners in relation to illegal activities associated with extremism, as well as social support for their families; (This activity will be implemented in coordination with MJ, MEST, MLSW, MCYS, as well as with the involvement of respective experts (psychologists) and representative of religious communities.)”¹⁵⁶ This strategy has been criticized on the basis that the main shortcomings of this strategy can be traced in its “structure, process and implementation.”¹⁵⁷ For instance, the study of “Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo” argues that in this strategy the roles of municipalities, local communities and NGOs are not specified. It is also mentioned that this strategy has failed to organize the budget plan and this has resulted in “ineffective and tangled budgeting at individual ministries’ level.”¹⁵⁸

A major finding in the Public Pulse analysis is that Kosovo Assembly must adopt a law that assigns the role and responsibilities of the ICK. Such a law would authorize ICK to control mosques and imams, a right which it does not have according to its internal rules. This suggestion is based on the fact that the main factors behind the spread of RE in Kosovo are the imams educated in the ME, imams appointed by those who funded the building of the mosques and the imams chosen by local people. The adoption of such a law seems an urgent matter because in this way the ICK would have the authority to appoint moderate imams and this would automatically result in the decrease of RE in Kosovo.

State institutions have been criticized for the lack of programs for de-radicalization and reintegration of individuals returned from terrorist armed conflicts in the ME. In order to identify and remove from the prisons the publications with the content of RE, it has been seized all the literature related to religion (excluding Qur’an). “Kosovo is actively tackling radicalization in prisons, reviewing and confiscating all religion-related literature in Kosovan prisons, except for the Quran ...”¹⁵⁹

156 Government of Kosovo, *Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020*, (2015), 25.

157 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 20.

158 Ibid., 21.

159 Ibid., 12.

Although it was a necessary step the removal of radical religious literature from Kosovo's correctional centres will not help to prevent the spread of RE if the prisoners are radicalized or may be easily victim of radicalization. Individuals convicted of terrorism can continue their jihad activities even inside the correctional institutions by radicalizing the other inmates.

In order to prevent this scenario the Ministry of Justice, in cooperation with ICK, has engaged some moderate imams to provide religious guidance for the purpose of rehabilitation and reintegration of individuals convicted of terrorism. In 2016, "the MJ of Kosovo and the KIC, have reached an agreement to engage 10 imams to provide services for prisoners as part of the support for rehabilitation and reintegration program for Syria and Iraq war-related offences."¹⁶⁰ The attempts of MJ in cooperation with ICK are necessary to rehabilitate and reintegrate radicalized prisoners. However, it does not solve it all because there may be convicted terrorists who do not feel guilty for their wrongdoings and refuse to talk to the appointed moderate imams or they may pretend to feel guilty only before the eyes of the authorities.

The MJ should focus more on strengthening the resilience against RE in prisons. The correctional institutions in Kosovo need comprehensive reforms, which would give prisoners the opportunity to various activities such as educational, cultural, sports and other activities. Involving prisoners in such activities would definitely increase the resilience inside prisons because in this way they would keep themselves busy. Working only with inmates who are convicted of terrorism may be seen as a discrimination or may be perceived as a "special treatment for the radicalized." It is also important to consider that there are cases when individuals charged with terrorism offences can be released as innocent if there is no convincing evidence to punish them. There may also be radical individuals who are unknown to the police and they can radicalize the society in a hidden way. Finally, even if the authorities manage to catch all the people involved in any terrorism activity within the territory of Kosovo, there is always the risk that comes from outside the borders. For instance, Kosovo authorities cannot arrest individuals who conduct online radicalization from the ME. Therefore, it is important to build resilience against RE in Kosovo, instead of just treating it with police methods.

160 Public Pulse Analysis on Prevention of Violent Extremism in Kosovo, (2017), 9.

7.1 Research Results

While strategies for the prevention of terrorism may be more effective in the consolidated countries where there is a good economy and social welfare, in a country like Kosovo where over 57% of the population is unemployed, such strategies do not make big difference. Under these conditions it is difficult for the state institutions to advise the people what to do, when it was demonstrated for many years that the political elite has worked for personal interests and not for the interests of the society. The efforts of public institutions against RE in Kosovo can easily be perceived by the society as anti-Islamic efforts because the state is showing concerns only about the rise of RE and not about the other negative activities happening in Kosovo. If treating terrorism with police methods is necessary to address the problem for a short-term, then the improvement of social welfare is definitely the right answer in treating this phenomenon for a long-term. Social welfare can be improved by increasing the morality of institutions, working sincerely for the creation of jobs, improvement of education system, culture, sports and so on. It is also essential to fight the factors that have drained the trust of citizens in the institutions of Kosovo, such as corruption, nepotism and organized crime. Fighting these factors is the right move to return people's trust in the public institutions and show them that the state of Kosovo does not belong to a particular group but to all humans living in Kosovo.

To change the topic, the initiative to provide moderate religious classes in public schools is necessary but, if the radical imams are allowed to spread their ideology outside the schools then we create two worlds that contradict and oppose each other. Therefore, it is more important to give chances to moderate religious leaders who are willing to work as imams in the mosques. In order to do so the adoption of a law which authorizes ICK to appoint and supervise the imams across the territory of Kosovo seems to be an urgent matter. Regarding educational system in Kosovo it is necessary that schools teach children comparative religion and at the same time make them able to think critically. To explain, the Kosovar society has heard the pronouncement given by Shefqet Krasniqi (the imam of the biggest mosque in Prishtina), he claimed that "all Christian believers belong to hell because they do not believe in Islam." As an illustration, when Shefqet Krasniqi was asked by an adherent whether Mother Theresa belongs in Heaven or Hell.

“In Hell, “he said with the confidence of the man who knows the future,” Mother Theresa, according to dr. Krasniqi, had a place in Jahannam (Hell), because she did not accept Allah ...”¹⁶¹ There are two ways to approach this wrongdoing. (1) For a short-term solution, Kosovo authorities should have arrested him right away and charged him with inciting hatred (treating terrorism as crime), but that happened only after it was confirmed that 316 citizens have joined terrorist armed groups in ME. (2) For a long-term solution, Kosovo institutions should focus on building resilience against RE (treating terrorism as disease). In order for this to happen it is essential to raise social awareness which would help to decode such remarks through critical thinking. For example, history teaches us that God created the world and mankind long before the Islam. According to Shefqet Krasniqi’s beliefs, God created the earth and mankind but forgot to create Islam. So, until the start of the 7th century, every human being went to hell because there was no religion to save them. It does not make any sense. As can be seen, the development of critical thinking would definitely increase the resilience of the society against RE, and at the same time, the radical imams would not gain as much popularity as today because they would sound irrational.

A good starting point to raise social awareness in Kosovo is to conduct social awareness campaigns through media such as radio, television, print media, social media and so on. Conducting such campaigns would definitely help to built resilience against RE in Kosovo. For instance, during the election time, political parties are very successful in doing political campaigns and spend large amounts of money without any hesitation. But when it comes to solving social issues such as RE, they lack the will to do so.

Considering the fact that the network of terrorist organizations is wide that reaches across borders then domestic, regional and international cooperation is a crucial factor in preventing terrorism. Regarding domestic cooperation, it is important that the central government, local governments, religious communities, civil society, and media work together when it comes to dealing with RE. Kosovo authorities should take immediate measures when citizens denounce radical imams to the police, and not wait until individuals turn to VA of terrorism. Given the fact that the spread of RE is not a problem only in Kosovo but in the entire region, Balkan countries should leave behind the historical context and work together in addressing this issue. This is important because fighting RE that leads to terrorism only in one country would mean nothing, if the RE is high in neighboring countries.

161 Veton Surroi, *Why should Shefqet Krasniqi be protected?*, (Zëri Daily Newspaper 2017), <<http://zeri.info/zerat/133548/perse-duhet-mbrojtur-shefqet-krasniqin/>> accessed 19 May 2018.

7.2 Conclusions and Recommendations

The first step to writing this paper was writing a project proposal consisting of mainly three research questions related to the research. After gathering and analyzing relevant literature that was vital in framing the theoretical chapters all the research questions that were used as pillars during the construction of this work can be answered. In order to find the right answers to these questions, it will be analyzed and elaborated all the material used for this study and also the findings of this research paper.

How resilient is the Kosovar society to RE?

RE in Kosovo is an influence that was brought after the war and it does not have old roots like in the region of the ME. The vast majority of Kosovo people appreciate the values of religious tolerance. Therefore, RE is not widely supported in Kosovo. A major factor that has contributed to the increase of religious tolerance in Kosovo, is that older generations used to practice one of the most moderate schools of Islam, called Hanafi. This tolerant interpretation of Islam allowed Muslim believers to adhere their religion and also live in harmony with the communities belonging to other religions. However, as consequence of numerous socio-economic problems and as a result of the interpretation of one of the most conservative schools of Islam after the war a considerable number of Kosovars became victims of RE. Apparently, RE found the right place and the right time to radicalize and manipulate a number of young people who did not have basic knowledge about religion. It is noted that during the post-war period people of Kosovo have become more religious. However, the concerns that one day Kosovo can be radicalized in large numbers is irrational. The great majority of the population are healthy and oriented towards the democratic values of the Western World. In order to preserve this society it is essential to improve the social welfare in Kosovo. This is because if they survive RE that leads to terrorism, they may not be able to survive other activities related to crime.

The strategies and other efforts of the state institutions to combat RE are necessary, but they never reach the desired effect when organized crime, corruption and nepotism are present within state institutions. Such attempts may be perceived by the society as anti-Islamic. For instance, people may think that the government is fighting RE just to please the international community, while corruption and organized crime are at the top of government. Unbalanced efforts to address a problem will not succeed if the society is

surrounded by many socio-economic problems. Therefore, the improvement of social welfare in Kosovo seems to be the right solution to address not only terrorism but also other problems that are choking the development of Kosovo in every aspect.

Was it possible to prevent RE in Kosovo?

If it has not been possible to prevent some negative experiences in post-war Kosovo the rise of RE could definitely be prevented. Before the war RE was not a factor in Kosovo. However, as a consequence of the war and poor political leadership, the society found itself in the middle of many difficulties and one of them was RE. Anyone who has lived in Kosovo before and after the war knows that RE has been brought from outside and it has no roots in Kosovo's traditions. As a result of several humanitarian organizations from the ME placed in Kosovo and some imams who were educated in the ME one of the most extremist schools of Islam was introduced. With the introduction of Hanbaliyya school misinterpretation of Islam and the incitement of hatred and intolerance started to become norms in the Muslim community. Despite the fact that incitement of hatred was prohibited by the Kosovo's Constitution and Criminal Code the Kosovo authorities did not take measures to prevent the rise of RE. As a consequence a considerable number of Kosovars were being victim of radicalization. They were dressing, speaking and behaving like Arabs. Therefore, there was no need for deep investigations to find out the individuals responsible for the spread of RE because such individuals could be noticed easily. The news that 316 citizens have joined armed terrorist groups in the ME did not surprise anyone in Kosovo but only the international partners. The religious extremists had gone so far with their misinterpretations that they began targeting even the most prominent national figures of Kosovo.

How to treat it: as war, crime, or disease?

An all-in-one answer would be the combined use of these three analogies to deal with terrorism. Usually developed countries fight terrorism with military actions, police methods and treat its causes and symptoms at the same time. Determining when to treat terrorism as war and when as crime or disease depends on the circumstances and on how policy makers view terrorism. For example, after 9/11 attacks many developed countries that used to

treat terrorism only as a crime, started to fight it as war (by military means) because they considered important to destroy the terrorist groups and organizations in the ME before they could have another chance (preemptive military strikes). However, concerning the war analogy, Kosovo is released of this responsibility. Kosovo has the Security Force but this force is permitted to carry only light weapons. Therefore, until the Kosovo Security Force is permitted to equip with heavy weaponry Kosovo should focus only on combating terrorism within its territory.

As has been mentioned, although late, Kosovo has succeeded in treating terrorism as crime. After it was confirmed that 316 citizens have joined terrorist armed groups in the ME, under the international pressure Kosovo Assembly passed a law which prohibits the participation of Kosovo citizens in foreign wars. Based on this law local authorities have arrested a considerable number of radical imams responsible for the spread of RE and also those who participated in terrorist armed conflicts in the ME and then returned to Kosovo. Also, in 2015 the Government of Kosovo has drafted a “Strategy on Prevention of Violent Extremism and Radicalization Leading to Terrorism 2015-2020.” All these efforts show that individuals who get involved in terrorism activities will be brought to justice and will be punished. The arrests of such individuals were extremely necessary to weaken the rise of RE in Kosovo but this is only a short-term solution because as it has been emphasized, the arrest and detention of such individuals does not mean that it will also extinguish their desires to do jihad.

If treating terrorism as crime is the right choice to deal with it over a short period of time, then treating terrorism as disease is definitely the right answer to deal with it over a long period of time. It has been elaborated above that even if the authorities manage to isolate all the pulling factors that caused the radicalization in the territory of Kosovo still there are pulling factors outside the borders where the hand of the government does not reach. Therefore, it is important that state institutions, religion communities and civil society work together in building resilience against RE that leads to terrorism. The resilience of the society can be strengthened by increasing the morality of institutions that would automatically result in the improvement of the education, culture and sports and so on. Considering the fact that more than half of the youth population in Kosovo are unemployed, creation of new jobs is an urgent need. The decrease of unemployment rates in Kosovo would result in the improvement of social welfare and, at the same time, the young people would not feel helpless in their own country. Fighting corruption, nepotism and organized crime in high-level is also crucial matter in order to restore citizens’ confidence that Kosovo institutions are working for the common good and not only for the interests of a particular group.

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